

ICT in Schools: A Boon or a Burden?

A systematic literature review

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Abstract

We provide a systematic literature review on the role of Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) in schools, focusing on empirical studies that exploit International Large-Scale Assessments (ILSAs) in European compulsory education. As ICT have become integral to students' everyday communication, information access, and learning activities, understanding their relationship with students' experience and competences is essential. We examine the extent to which educational results in compulsory schooling hold across countries using evidence from 112 ILSA-based empirical studies. Despite the heterogeneity of the evidence, recurrent patterns can be identified. Firstly, it is evident that the mere availability of ICT cannot be considered a differential factor in the context of European countries. Secondly, the frequency of ICT use is of greater significance than its mere utilisation. The payoff to ICT use have been shown to exhibit a tendency for decreasing returns, often following an inverted-U shape. Thirdly, there is a clear positive relationship between students' ICT engagement and ICT use.

JEL classification: ...

Keywords: Information and communication technologies; systematic literature review; school system; international large-scale assessments

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1 Background and motivations

1.1 ICT is relevant from a historical perspective and a political aspect

Information and communication technologies (ICT) are defined as a “diverse set of technological tools and resources used to communicate and to create, disseminate, store, and manage information” (Blurton, 1999). The definition of ICT includes all types of hardware, such as computers, the internet, mobile phones and television, as well as software such as operating systems, applications and platforms. The presence and use of ICT has grown significantly since the early 2000s in educational contexts (Comi et al., 2017; Falck et al., 2018). This growth has occurred mainly for two reasons. First, technological progress has made technology increasingly integrated into people’s lives and increasingly accessible to all (Skryabin et al., 2015). Second, policies to introduce ICT tools into classrooms have become commonplace in all countries and this process has been driven by substantial investment (Angrist & Lavy, 2002; De Witte & Rogge, 2014; Spiezia, 2010). While the initial reason is still evolving, with the advent of artificial intelligence transforming the manner in which students learn, the second reason is the subject of significant debate. A school of thought is evolving that is in opposition to the integration of technology within educational settings. This development reflects debates among researchers and policymakers about the actual contribution of technology to learning processes (Schleicher, 2019). Several countries, including France, Italy and Sweden, have banned the use of mobile phones in schools (Böttger & Zierer, 2024; Campbell et al., 2024; Kessel et al., 2020; Selwyn & Aagaard, 2021). These policies are derived from unclear findings regarding the effect of ICT on learning outcomes (C. Hu, 2017; Livingstone, 2012). This has led scholars in both education economics and pedagogy to argue that the use of technology in education should be carefully assessed and contextually evaluated. In this historical context, the impact of ICT on academic outcomes has become a controversial issue worthy of attention (Fernández-Gutiérrez et al., 2020).

1.2 Our focus on EU countries

This systematic review of the literature focuses primarily on studies that include at least one European Union (EU) country in their analysis. However, this does not imply the exclusion of research from other countries. On the contrary, non-European contexts serve as useful points of comparison, offering insights into the relative positioning of the European education system in the global landscape. The decision to focus on studies with at least one EU presence is based on two main considerations. The first is the reduction of heterogeneity. One of the main challenges in conducting a systematic review of this type is the high degree of heterogeneity between studies, particularly with regard to institutional structures, economic conditions and education policies. This choice allows us to exclude studies focusing exclusively on countries whose educational systems differ substantially from those of the EU. This approach balances specificity and generalisability, ensuring

that the results remain relevant beyond the European context without being weakened by excessive geographical variability (Caena, 2019; Redecker & Punie, 2017). The second is the EU's institutional role in ICT development. Despite national differences, EU-level initiatives and funding programmes, such as the Digital Education Action Plan (European Commission, 2020) and Horizon Europe, have fostered a common trajectory in the adoption and implementation of digital technologies in member states' education systems. Although the EU education landscape is not uniform, it is characterised by relatively aligned policy objectives, particularly with regard to digitisation, inclusion and innovation in education (European Commission, 2020; OECD, 2023, 2025).

1.3 Empirical analysis based on ILSAs

Over the past two decades, numerous studies have examined links between ICT and educational outcomes. Broadly, they fall into two categories: (i) experimental and quasi-experimental designs that identify causal effects of ICT on learning, and (ii) empirical analyses using international large-scale assessments (e.g., PISA, PIRLS and TIMSS) that yield robust cross-country evidence on students' cognitive outcome. The former is based on a specific research design to analyse the causal relationship. Consequently, the external validity of these studies is limited (De Witte & Rogge, 2014). It is important to note that the reference sample differs for each study, and the variables utilised are also at the discretion of the researchers, which has a direct impact on the comparability of the results. Furthermore, increasing the reference sample would in many cases mean a significant increase in the cost of the research. In contrast, the latter stream of literature (evaluations using large-scale assessments) finds itself in a different situation. Cross-sectional data from international surveys is utilised, enabling analyses with greater external validity. However, the inability to identify causal links remains a limitation. The focus of this group of studies is on statistical associations between ICT variables and educational outcomes at the student level, due to the problem of endogeneity (Biagi & Loi, 2013; Fariña et al., 2015; Spiezia, 2010). In recent years, literature has managed to limit endogeneity through different and innovative methodologies, such as Bayesian Additive Regression Trees (BART) (Cabras & Tena Horrillo, 2016; Ferraro, 2018; Veselkova, 2024), Mahalanobis Matching Approach (De Witte & Rogge, 2014), and Propensity Score Matching (Agasisti et al., 2020).

1.4 A systematic review of the literature and research questions

A systematic review provides a rigorous and transparent approach to summarising the existing literature. The broad scope of ICT makes it difficult to identify straightforward relationships between technology use and student outcomes. Instead, several mechanisms have been identified, such as frequency of use, students' engagement with technology, and the purposes for which it is employed. These factors operate within an educational environment that is inherently complex and shaped by multiple interdependent variables.

In this study, we focus on key aspects emerging from previous work. Specifically, we examine two main lines of inquiry: first, the methodological approaches adopted to analyse the role of ICT in the production of educational outcomes; and second, the typologies and classifications of ICT most frequently discussed in previous research, synthesising the main empirical findings emerging from the literature. Accordingly, we address two research questions:

- RQ1: What research methods have been employed to study the relationship between ICT and student performance?
- RQ2: Which aspects of ICT have the strongest association with student performance?

2 The methodology

The methodological approach of this study is based on a systematic literature review. Systematic reviews play a crucial role in research as they aim to provide a rigorous and comprehensive response to a specific research question (Kitchenham et al., 2010). By adopting a structured and transparent methodology, systematic reviews seek to minimize bias and enhance the accuracy and reliability of findings (Gough et al., 2017). Moreover, they ensure an exhaustive synthesis of the available evidence, facilitating the integration of insights from multiple sources. This, in turn, enhances the generalizability of results and strengthens the empirical foundation of the research (Chalmers et al., 2002). The first step involves defining specific eligibility criteria to ensure a transparent selection process for contributions from the literature (Moher et al., 2009). Within these constraints, a structured synthesis is developed, integrating the diverse perspectives presented in the literature. The objective is to provide a comprehensive overview of the research scope while adhering to the principles of rigorous scientific inquiry. The reporting process followed the guiding principles of the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) (Page et al., 2021). The PRISMA framework was applied to structure the description of inclusion criteria, data sources, collection methods, analysed items, and result synthesis.

2.1 *Search and query strategy*

Conducting a systematic review on the role of ICT in student outcomes presents significant challenges for two main reasons. First, the complexity of the educational ecosystem makes it difficult to isolate relationships between variables. Student achievement is influenced by multiple factors operating at the student, school, and broader environmental levels, all of which contribute to the potential spurious relationship between technology and academic performance. Second, the extensive body of literature on this topic has

expanded significantly over the past two decades. ICT in education has been examined across multiple disciplines, including economics, sociology, management, pedagogy, and education, resulting in a vast and rapidly expanding body of research. Our goal is to assemble a broad and inclusive set of peer-reviewed studies. At the same time, we apply clear selection criteria to ensure a consistent analytical focus and a corpus of studies appropriate for the empirical assessment carried out in this review. For this reason, studies were sourced using the Scopus search engine (Elsevier, 2025). Scopus is widely recognized as a leading academic database, ensuring the selection of peer-reviewed journal articles that meet rigorous scientific standards. A second limitation concerns the focus on ILSAs. This choice reflects the objective of conducting a systematic review of studies based on a common data framework. ILSAs provide the most extensive cross-country dataset in education, enabling comparative analyses across different contexts using standardized variables. Among these, OECD-PISA (Programme for International Student Assessment) is the most widely used and recognized assessment. Two other major international surveys are developed by the International Association for the Evaluation of Educational Achievement (IEA): TIMSS (Trends in International Mathematics and Science Study), which focuses on mathematics and science achievement, and PIRLS (Progress in International Reading Literacy Study), which assesses reading literacy. A third constraint is the exclusive selection of studies that employ quantitative methodologies. This criterion eliminates theoretical papers and studies based on qualitative analysis. In addition, we set the time frame from the year 2000 to March 2025, when the final search was conducted. This restriction is justified by two main reasons. First, ILSAs began implementation around this period, with PISA launching in 2000 and other assessments following later. Second, the study of technology in education gained prominence during this timeframe, particularly accelerating in the 2010s. An additional criterion is the focus on ICT. Therefore, we include only studies that explicitly examine technology within the school environment. This criterion covers all aspects of technology, including basic computer access, availability, purposes and locations of use, attitudes toward ICT, and students' ICT engagement. Finally, the unit of analysis is compulsory schooling, consistent with ILSAs, which assess students at different stages of primary and secondary education in participating countries.

Based on the criteria listed above, we constructed the query. The main challenge was to develop a strategy that minimised false positives while retaining high sensitivity to relevant contributions. As an initial step, we adopted a search-snowball procedure to identify the terminology most commonly used in the field. To achieve this, we reviewed multiple studies, extracting frequently used terms, particularly from titles, abstracts, and keywords. This process ultimately led to the formulation of the query reported in table 1. This query is structured into four groups, each corresponding to a specific research constraint.

The first group addresses ICT and its various terminologies across studies. Depending on the context, "ICT" may be replaced by broader terms such as "technology" or

Table 1: Search–query strategy

Group	Query terms
ICT terms	“ICT” or “technolog*” or “digital learning” or “computer*”
Link to outcomes	“effect*” or “relationship” or “achievement” or “evaluation” or “influence” or “efficiency”
ILSAs context	“PISA” or “TIMSS” or “PIRLS” or “test standard” or “ILSAs” or “large scale assessments”
Education scope	“school*” or “education”

"technological," while in other cases, expressions like "digital learning" are used. Additionally, in earlier literature, some researchers refer to "computers" when analyzing the relationship between device usage and student achievement. The second group focuses on the relationship between ICT and student achievement, which is the core of this research. This category includes all terms found in the analysed studies that describe the link between technology and student outcomes. The third group concerns ILSAs, encompassing explicit references to the three main international assessments (PISA, TIMSS, and PIRLS) as well as more general terms such as "standardized tests," "ILSAs," or "large-scale assessments." This approach reflects the tendency in the literature to mention widely recognized assessments like PISA, TIMSS, or PIRLS without necessarily using broader classification terms. Finally, the fourth group pertains to the school context and the education sector, ensuring the inclusion of studies relevant to this field while filtering out contributions from unrelated disciplines. The choice of two broad terms is justified by their frequent use in studies addressing educational topics.

Table 2: Filters applied to the Scopus search

Filter	Specification
Publication years	2000–2025
Source type	Journals
Publication stage	Final publications only
Document type	Articles
Subject areas	Social Sciences, Computer Science, Engineering, Mathematics, Economics, Decision Sciences, Business, Neuroscience, Multidisciplinary
Language	English

The number of papers from this query is 659. To ensure a rigorous and relevant selection of studies, we applied several filters to the search query (see table 2). First, we restricted the selection to publications from 2000 onward. We also limited the search to peer-reviewed academic journal articles (j) in their final version (final) to ensure source quality and reliability. Regarding document type, only research articles (ar) were included, excluding conference proceedings, reviews, and editorials. The selection was

further refined by focusing on subject areas relevant to our analysis, including social sciences (SOC), computer science (COMP), engineering (ENGI), mathematics (MATH), economics (ECON), decision sciences (DECI), business (BUSI), neuroscience (NEUR), and multidisciplinary studies (MULT). Finally, to maintain linguistic consistency and broad accessibility, only studies published in English were considered (English). The sample was restricted to these filters. The outcome of this process was the identification of 369 papers.

2.2 *Screening strategy*

From the 369 records identified in the initial search, a specific screening strategy was adopted. A preliminary screening was conducted by reviewing the title, abstract, and keywords to exclude studies that were clearly irrelevant to our research question. This selection process was guided by three main exclusion criteria: (i) Absence of an ICT focus. Studies that did not specifically address ICT or, more broadly, the application of technology in education were excluded. (ii) Data not derived from ILSAs. Papers that did not utilise data from ILSAs were excluded to ensure comparability and robustness in the analysis. (iii) Absence of an EU country in the analysis. Studies that did not include at least one EU member state in their empirical analysis were excluded.

While the first two criteria align with the methodological approach adopted, the third criterion warrants particular attention. The decision to focus on the European context is motivated by the aim of examining the role of ICT within European education systems. Although technology itself is largely standardised on a global scale, its educational impact is heavily shaped by the socioeconomic, cultural, and institutional contexts in which it is implemented. ICT should not be treated as a neutral input, independent of social and territorial conditions, but as a factor whose effects are shaped by the contexts in which it is embedded. This exclusion criterion did not remove all non-European evidence but simply limited geographical bias. Studies focused solely on non-EU regions were excluded, whereas global analyses including at least one European country were retained. This approach keeps the review centred on the European educational context while still allowing relevant international comparisons.

Following the application of the exclusion criteria, 247 documents were eliminated. Figure 3 illustrates the flow chart showing the different stages of the systematic review. After this selection, 122 articles progressed to the third stage, where an in-depth analysis was performed through a full-text review. The eligibility criteria used to determine the relevance of the contributions were the methodological consistency of the data used, the appropriateness of the research focus, and the geographical relevance.

At this stage, 16 papers were excluded. Of these, 7 contributions were removed as they focused on comparing standardised test results administered in different formats -

Figure 3: The PRISMA flow diagram

computer-based versus paper-based. Since this issue pertains more to the theoretical dimension of technology’s role in test administration rather than its broader impact on education, these studies were not included. A further 2 papers were excluded due to the use of mixed data sources, combining ILSA data with other datasets, mainly secondary analyses conducted on a small sample of individuals. This decision aligns with our objective of focusing exclusively on the evidence generated by ILSAs in this field of research. Finally, 7 papers were excluded due to the absence of EU countries in their analysis. This geographical irrelevance only became apparent upon thorough full-text review.

As a final step, we employed a backward search approach. This methodology involves reviewing the reference lists of selected studies to identify additional relevant literature (Briscoe et al., 2020). By systematically applying our inclusion and exclusion criteria to these references, we ensured that only studies meeting our eligibility requirements were considered for full-text review. At the end of this process, we identified and included 6 additional papers. These studies exhibited two key characteristics: they had been cited a substantial number of times by the papers in our review and met the predefined inclusion, exclusion, and eligibility criteria.

In conclusion, after completing the full screening procedure and the backward-search process, the final sample consists of 112 studies. This number is consistent with the scope of academic reviews in educational technology. Lai and Bower (2019) report that, based on 32 systematic reviews, the average sample size is 73 papers, with values ranging from 10 to 176.

2.3 *Conducting the review*

The relevant information for each paper was collected in accordance with the research questions. The data was systematically recorded in an Excel spreadsheet. Given the inherent complexity of the process, any ambiguity present in a paper was addressed through collaborative discussion by the research team until a consensus was reached on both data extraction and categorisation.

The data collection process was meticulously organised into two primary sections. The first document contained general information about each paper, while the second focused on variables directly related to the research questions.

The initial section comprised the following fields: the following details are to be provided for each article: author details (AU); paper title (TP); journal (J); year of publication (YP); and the unique article identifier (DOI). The second section comprised the following: The data utilised for the analysis (ILSA); the assessment wave considered (WAVE); the countries analysed (COUNTRY); the performance outcome examined (OUTPUT); the type of analysis (TYPE) — indicating whether the study aimed to identify associative, causal, or efficiency relationships; the methodology employed (METHOD); the specific ICT focus (FOCUS); the classification number of the focus (GROUP) — explained in the following subsection; the direction of the results (RESULT) — whether positive, negative, null, or mixed; other relevant aspects (OTHER); and notes on findings (NOTE).

Two classificatory dimensions employed in the review merit particular attention: the methodological approach and the role attributed to ICT. The first classification is predicated on the methodological objective of each study. The majority of contributions adopt an associative approach, encompassing associative, correlational, predictive, or mediation relationships between variables. The objective of these studies is to identify statistical links between ICT use and student outcomes, without assuming a direct causal connection. A smaller group of papers adopts a causal approach, seeking to move beyond simple associations and to identify causal effects of technology use on educational outcomes. As will be demonstrated in the results section, the limited number of causal studies reflects both data constraints and the methodological challenges involved in designing models that can credibly estimate causal effects. A third group, which is less represented, comprises efficiency analyses. Within this subset, only one study (Mergoni et al., 2023) explicitly examines ICT as a determinant of educational efficiency, while other treats digital technologies as one of several inputs included in the efficiency estimation models. Further details on methodological approaches and their distribution across studies are presented in the results section 3.2.

The second classification concerns the specific aspect of ICT examined in each study. Following an comprehensive review of the literature and discussions within the research team, three main categories were identified. The initial group pertains to the access and availability of ICT. This covers all studies that analyse the presence and distribution of

digital resources, both within and outside of the school environment. Examples of such factors include the number of computers in schools, the availability of Internet connections in classrooms, and the presence of digital infrastructure in students' homes. The second group focusses on the use and frequency of ICT use. This category is characterised by greater heterogeneity than the previous one, encompassing variables pertaining to the manner, location and rationale behind the use of digital tools. These tools may be employed for academic or recreational purposes, within or outside the educational setting (e.g., at home or social settings). The frequency and intensity of use are also central to this category, as they capture the extent of students' interaction with technology. The third group corresponds to ICT engagement, as defined for instance in the PISA framework under the label of cognitive-motivational engagement (see Kunina-Habenicht and Goldhammer (2020)) which is theoretically based on self-determination theory (Ryan & Deci, 2000). The study encompasses variables related with students' attitudes and perceptions regarding ICT utilisation, including self-perceived digital competence, autonomy in technological usage, general attitudes towards ICT, and personal interest in technology (Zylka et al., 2015). This dimension has attracted increased attention in recent years, as it is increasingly recognised as a potential mediator or moderator in the relationship between ICT use and educational performance.

3 Results

The results section is divided into two distinct parts. The first part provides a bibliometric analysis, offering a descriptive overview of the examined literature. The analysis provides information on the publication year, the journal, the data sources used and the performance measures employed. The second part addresses the core of the systematic review, that is, the response to research questions. It delivers a methodological and interpretative analysis of the evidence presented in the selected studies, with particular attention to the methodological approaches employed and the various aspects of ICT that are related to students' performance.

3.1 *Bibliometric analysis*

As illustrated by Figure 4, the distribution of publication years across the 112 studies examined is shown. The data demonstrate a consistent upward trend, reflecting the increasing academic interest in the role of ICT in education and the growing use of ILSA data to investigate this relationship.

Figure 4: Figure 4: Number of papers by year of publication

The sample of 112 studies captures the school context from multiple perspectives. Given that the analysis is conducted within the ILSA framework, the studies are based on compulsory education, with 92% focusing on secondary education (102 studies), 6% on primary education (8 studies), and the remaining share comprising two studies that address both educational levels. It should be noted that, in the case of primary education, the grade most frequently analysed is the fourth grade, typically through studies based on TIMSS and PIRLS. For secondary education, analyses generally focus on eighth grade when using TIMSS or ICILS¹. In contrast, PISA does not adopt a grade-based sampling design; students are selected by age - specifically 15-year-olds - which, in most European education systems, corresponds to Grade 10.

¹ICILS (International Computer and Information Literacy Study) is an international large-scale assessment conducted by the International Association for the Evaluation of Educational Achievement (IEA), aimed at measuring students' computer and information literacy.

Table 5: Data studied divided by ILSAs

Dataset	Wave(s)	Number of Papers
PISA		99
Programme for International Student Assessment		
	<i>Single wave studies</i>	88
	2000	1
	2003	2
	2006	6
	2009	10
	2012	13
	2015	19
	2018	34
	2022	3
	<i>Longitudinal studies</i>	11
	2000 - 2003 - 2006 - 2009 - 2012	2
	2000 - 2003 - 2006 - 2009 - 2012 - 2015 - 2018	1
	2003 - 2006	1
	2006 - 2009 - 2012 - 2015 - 2018	1
	2009 - 2015	1
	2009 - 2012 - 2015	1
	2009 - 2012 - 2015 - 2018	3
	2015 - 2018	1
TIMSS		6
Trends in International Mathematics and Science Study		
	2011	2
	2015	2
	2003 - 2007 - 2011	1
	2011 - 2015	1
PIRLS		4
Progress in International Reading Literacy Study		
	2016	1
	2021	1
	2001 - 2006	1
	2001 - 2006 - 2011	1
ICILS		1
International Computer and Information Literacy Study		
	2018	1
MIXED		2
	TIMSS 2011 - PIRLS 2011 - PISA 2012	1
	TIMSS 2019 - PIRLS 2016	1

Note: Author's own elaboration.

Table 5 shows the ILSAs used in the review. A clear centrality of PISA data emerges

within the literature. PISA has become the benchmark reference for analyses based on ILSAs, both at the cross-national level and, increasingly, in national studies that rely on international data sources (Hopfenbeck et al., 2018). In total, 99 studies (88%) use PISA data. The remaining contributions are distributed among TIMSS (6 studies), PIRLS (4 studies), and ICILS (1 study). Additionally, 2 studies adopt a mixed approach, drawing on two or more ILSAs simultaneously. There are also 15 longitudinal studies, which compare two or more waves of the same ILSA to capture temporal trends in the phenomenon under investigation.

It is also worth examining how frequently different waves of PISA data are used across the selected studies. This allows us to explore whether specific survey cycles have attracted greater attention from the academic community. As expected, there is a growing trend in the number of analyses over time, with PISA 2018 being the most widely used wave, featured in 34 studies. The lower presence of the 2022 wave is mainly due to the limited time that has elapsed since its release, which has not yet allowed for the publication of extensive analyses using these data.

Table 6: Students’ performance dimensions studied

Performance Dimension	Number of Papers
<i>Pure cognitive performance</i>	91
Reading	23
Mathematics	18
Science	9
Reading and Mathematics	2
Mathematics and Science	7
Reading, Mathematics and Science	32
<i>Other performance</i>	21
ICT-based (ICT attitudes, ICT use, digital competence, school digital inclusion)	13
other-based (financial, problem solving, global competence, loneliness, boredom)	8

Note: Author’s own elaboration.

Table 6 presents the specific learning domains investigated. The majority of papers concentrate on the conventional competencies evaluated by ILSAs, namely reading, mathematics, and science. However, within this group, different analytical approaches can be identified. The focus of some studies is on a single subject area, while others examine all three domains in unison. A secondary subset focuses on STEM-related skills (mathematics and science) or on mathematics and reading exclusively. The latter configuration frequently typifies studies from the early 2000s, a period when science had not yet attained the same level of significance within international assessments. Furthermore, several pa-

pers extend beyond the traditional academic domains to investigate student performance in other areas, most notably ICT or digital competence itself, as well as related constructs such as financial literacy or problem-solving skills.

Table 7: Distribution of reviewed papers by journal

Journal	Number of papers
Computers & Education	24
Education and Information Technologies	8
Large-Scale Assessments in Education	5
Sustainability	3
Journal of Educational Computing Research	3
Eurasia Journal of Mathematics, Science and Technology Education	3
International Journal of Educational Development	3
Socio-Economic Planning Sciences	2
Mathematics	2
Learning and Individual Differences	2
Journal of Computer Assisted Learning	2
Revista de Educación	2
Education Economics	2
British Journal of Educational Technology	2
British Educational Research Journal	2
International Journal of Educational Research	2
Oxford Bulletin of Economics and Statistics	1
Journal of Educational Psychology	1
Educational Studies	1
Empirica	1
Education Inquiry	1
Australian Journal of Education	1
Review of Education	1
European Education	1
Transactions on Learning Technologies	1
European Educational Research Journal	1
Chinese Sociological Review	1
European Journal of Education	1
Omega	1
European Journal of Educational Research	1
Quality and Quantity	1
European Sociological Review	1

Continued on next page

Journal	Number of papers
Social Indicators Research	1
Heliyon	1
Educational Technology & Society	1
Humanities and Social Sciences Communications	1
Journal of Educational Multimedia and Hypermedia	1
Interactive Learning Environments	1
Journal of New Approaches in Educational Research	1
Computers and Education Open	1
Cogent Education	1
International Journal of Educational Psychology	1
OECD Journal: Economic Studies	1
Turkish Online Journal of Educational Technology	1
Orbis Scholae	1
Annual Review of CyberTherapy and Telemedicine	1
PLoS One	1
International Journal of Research & Method in Education	1
Research in Science & Technological Education	1
International Journal of Science and Mathematics Education	1
Educational Research and Evaluation	1
International Journal of STEM Education	1
Social Psychology of Education	1
Journal of Applied Statistics	1
Studies in Educational Evaluation	1
Journal of Business Research	1
Texto Livre	1
Computers in Human Behavior	1
Educational Technology and Society	1
Computers in the Schools	1
International Journal of Educational Research and Innovation (IJERI)	1
Total	112

Table 7 provides an overview of the academic journals in which the studies included in the review were published. The most represented journals are Computers & Education (24 studies), Education and Information Technologies (8 studies), and Large-Scale Assessments in Education (5 studies). Despite this concentration, there is a notable heterogeneity in publication venues, reflecting the multidisciplinary interest in the topic.

The geographical coverage of the studies included in the review is highly heterogeneous. While Europe is the most frequently examined region, reflecting the inclusion

criteria adopted, many contributions also draw on broader international samples in line with the cross-national design of ILSAs.

In summary, the bibliometric analysis shows that the 112 studies included in the review constitute a highly heterogeneous body of work, varying in the ILSAs and waves employed, the outcomes examined, the journals of publication, and the countries covered. This heterogeneity should be considered a value for our purpose because the evidence emerging from their analysis can be considered very valid externally.

3.2 *Findings: the methods employed for the empirical analysis*

The analysis of the papers included in this systematic review reveals the presence of three distinct inferential approaches: associative analysis, causal analysis, and, finally, efficiency analysis (see Table 8). Each approach is based on a different formulation of the research question and is implemented through specific methodological strategies, each with its analytical objectives, strengths, and limitations. Among the three, the associative approach is by far the most prevalent, accounting for more than 90% of the studies. This outcome was expected: although ILSA data provide a rich and comparable informational base, they are not easily suited to causal identification strategies (Cordero et al., 2018). All studies included in this review rely on observational and cross-sectional data drawn from ILSAs. Consequently, researchers cannot fully control for the factors that simultaneously influence both ICT and student performance. This raises potential endogeneity concerns, such as omitted variable bias, reverse causality, or measurement error, that may distort the estimated relationships (Webbink, 2005). For example, more motivated or higher-achieving students may also tend to use ICT more frequently, generating correlations that do not necessarily imply causal effects. Addressing these issues would require quasi-experimental or longitudinal designs, or the use of valid instrumental variables, which are often unfeasible given the structure of ILSAs.

Table 8: Methods used in analyses

Methodological category	Number of papers
Association approach	102
Causal approach	8
Efficiency approach	2
<i>Total</i>	112

3.2.1 **Associative analysis**

The objective of associative analysis is to identify statistical relationships between observed variables, with a particular focus on those associated with ICT and student academic outcomes. These studies aim to uncover systematic links between ICT availability,

usage, frequency of use, and student engagement with technology, and the various dimensions of academic performance. It is common practice for such models to control for a wide range of covariates, including the country’s level of development, the school’s resource endowments and organisational characteristics, and students’ and families’ socio-economic status (SES). Estimated effects may capture spurious correlations rather than genuine causal relationships (Biagi & Loi, 2013).

Table 9: Number of papers by association method

Methodological category	Number of papers
Descriptive statistics	7
Single-level regression models	22
Multilevel regression models	43
Structural models (SEM / Multilevel SEM)	15
Machine Learning	4
Hybrid approaches	11
<i>Total</i>	102

This approach is employed in 102 papers (see Table 9). A diverse set of methodologies is represented within this group. The most common are regression-based techniques, including both single-level - 22 papers - and multilevel models. Multilevel analysis - used in 43 studies - is the most frequently applied method, reflecting the hierarchical structure of ILSA educational data (e.g., country, school, classroom, student). The second most prominent group comprises structural models, particularly Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) and Multilevel SEM, which are employed in 15 papers. These techniques allow researchers to examine more complex dimensions of the relationship between ICT and learning outcomes, such as latent constructs like student engagement with technology. A third, emerging group includes studies adopting Machine Learning (ML) approaches. While still relatively uncommon, their use is increasing. These methods are especially valued for their computational capacity and flexibility in handling high-dimensional data structures. In addition, the literature includes a small number of studies using basic descriptive statistics (7 studies) and some hybrid models (11 studies) that combine multiple methodological strategies within a single analytical framework. In many cases, the methodological design includes an initial pre-processing phase, involving dimensionality reduction techniques, such as Principal Component Analysis (PCA) or Categorical Principal Component Analysis (CATPCA), or latent classification approaches, such as Latent Class Analysis (LCA) or Latent Profile Analysis (LPA). This is followed by an explicit modeling stage, typically conducted through regression models, which leverage the outcomes of the exploratory phase.

Despite its non-causal nature, associative analysis retains considerable descriptive and interpretative value. It helps identify relational patterns, clusters of students or schools,

and observable dynamics within the broader educational framework.

Descriptive analysis The analysis firstly considers the seven descriptive papers. These studies rely on descriptive statistics to outline patterns and basic associations between ICT and student performance, without applying inferential models. The evidence suggests that moderate ICT use tends to support student achievement, while recreational use shows no benefits. The integration of ICT within the school environment, when pedagogically appropriate, has been shown to have a positive effect.

The first paper (Kadijevich, 2015) analysed TIMSS data from 2003 to 2011 to assess whether computer use has any correlation with mathematics results. The study found that frequent use of computers had a negative correlation with mathematics achievement. Computers used as a learning tool (for exploring principles and practicing skills) showed a more positive impact on achievement compared to their use as an information tool (for looking up information and processing data). In contrast to Kadijevich, all six other papers utilised data from PISA. Using data from wave 2006, Kubiato and Vlckova (2010) highlighted a positive relationship between ICT use and scientific knowledge when ICT is linked to the educational process. Tømte and Hatlevik (2011) with the same wave, for students in Finland and Norway, pointed out how higher ICT self-efficacy is associated with more frequent ICT use, with gender gaps favouring males. Steffens (2014) emphasised that the relationship between ICT use and PISA 2009 achievements follows an inverted U-shape. Moderate ICT use correlates with better performance, whereas high-frequency ICT use correlates with lower achievement, particularly in leisure-related activities. Vázquez-Cano et al. (2020) used PISA 2015 data for 21 countries to observe the use of ICT on reading performance. It showed how excessive use of digital devices for non-academic activities outside school negatively impacts reading performance, with activities like playing online games and uploading self-created content being particularly detrimental. Furthermore, for PISA 2018, Navarro-Martinez and Peña-Acuña (2022) examined data on Spanish students. The results indicate that excessive use (i.e., every day) of social networks for online gaming is negatively associated with academic performance, while communication via social networks shows a positive association. Furthermore, the data indicate that males are more exposed to this detrimental role of ICT for online gaming activities, as earlier internet use correlates with a higher probability of lower academic scores. Finally, the last paper in this group is by Siebecke and Jarl (2022) which highlights results for resilient schools in Sweden for all available waves, i.e. from 2000 to 2018. Resilient schools decreased from 14% in 2000 to 3% in 2015. However, no significant differences were found in the material well-being between resilient and non-resilient schools, including the availability of computers and other educational resources, suggesting that similar levels of resource availability do not necessarily lead to similar academic outcomes.

Single-level regression models A second group of studies, consisting of 22 contributions, employs single regression models to examine the association between ICT and their academic performance in ILSAs. In these works, ICT is treated as an independent variable or as a set of specific indicators (access, frequency and purpose of use, attitudes), while student performance represents the dependent outcome. These models generally incorporate basic controls for sociodemographic factors (e.g. gender, SES - socioeconomic status, or family background). However, they do not take into account more complex structural relations or indirect effects. Despite the fact that this approach provides a preliminary level of statistical inference in comparison to exclusively descriptive analyses, it remains fundamentally cross-sectional and associative in nature.

A seminal and early contribution to this field is provided by Spiezia (2010), who evaluates how computer use at home and at school influences students' skills using PISA 2006 data. The author finds that computer use increases students' performance in science, having controlled for both observable (spurious correlation) and unobservable (selection) differences between students, their families and their schools. The real driver of this increase seems to be computer use at home, while the effect of computer use at school is almost negligible. Furthermore, a positive result is more evident when considering frequent use, i.e. almost every day, rather than a few times a month. Published in 2010, this study introduced a focus on the contextual dimension of ICT use, underlining its relevance for understanding educational outcomes. Next, Güzeller and Akin (2014) use data from PISA 2006 to show how ICT indicators explain a small but significant proportion of the variance in mathematics scores, with an average of 11% and a range from 2% to 24%. Frequent and recreational use of technology tends to be associated with poorer results, while confidence and perceived competence in the use of ICT is associated with better results. Also using PISA 2006, Drabowicz (2014) examines how gender shapes patterns of ICT use. Using a logit version of the ordinal regression model, it found that boys use ICT more for both educational and entertainment purposes. Girls outperform boys only when ICT is used to communicate with others. In conclusion, gender inequality in ICT usage among adolescents persists in all countries, mainly in favour of boys.

There are four papers that focus on PISA 2009. Biagi and Loi (2013) showed, through multivariate regressions, the link between ICT usage intensity and performance. The results indicate that gaming-only ICT activities have a positive coefficient between test scores and usage intensity. It is negative indeed for creation on content and knowledge and problem solving activities. Giambona and Porcu (2015) used the Italian sample with a quantile regression approach to assess differences between the determinants of reading achievement among students from different backgrounds. The results show that ICT availability at home and ICT resources for learning at home positively affect reading achievement, especially for lower-performing students, while ICT resources at school do not have a significant effect. Lee and Wu (2012, 2013) use PISA 2009 data to analyse how ICT use and online activities relate to reading literacy. They show that positive ICT at-

titudes, ICT self-efficacy, and information-seeking activities support reading performance primarily through online-reading engagement and metacognitive strategy use. ICT availability at home shows mixed or negative direct effects, while ICT resources at school display none. By contrast, social-entertainment activities are negatively associated with both metacognition and reading, whereas purposeful information-seeking online appears beneficial for literacy.

For the 2012 wave, only one study is available. It is particularly relevant, as it introduced the discussion on attitudes toward ICT use, a dimension that can be regarded as part of ICT engagement. Petko et al. (2017) performed a weighted OLS regression for each of the 39 countries analysed. The study finds that positive attitudes towards ICT as a learning tool are generally associated with higher test scores across the three subjects. The frequency of ICT use at school is generally negatively associated with performance. In conclusion, this paper shows that positive attitudes towards ICT, reflecting high-quality digital learning experiences, are associated with higher scores, suggesting that the quality of ICT use matters more than its frequency.

Dong and Kula (2023) and Rozgonjuk et al. (2021) analysed the 2015 wave. Dong et al. implemented an endogenous treatment effects model to investigate the impact of different frequencies of ICT use for school-related purposes on students' science achievement. The authors showed that the factor driving the positive relationship between ICT use and higher science scores is ICT use at home, while use at school is negatively correlated. The results are consistent with the argument advanced by Bingimlas (2009), which underscores the central role of contextual factors in ICT use and the persistent lack of confidence and competence among teachers. The second paper focuses on Estonia and demonstrates the importance of not using the internet excessively (Rozgonjuk et al., 2021). The authors indicate that a threshold of 60 minutes per day must be maintained to ensure a positive relationship between ICT use and better academic results. Conversely, using the internet for more than six hours a day has an extremely negative impact, even when controlling for students' socioeconomic status and gender. Moreover, Sun et al. (2024) also showed the effects of ICT use in schools on scientific skills. In particular, they focused on students with higher-order thinking skills following the taxonomy of Marzano and Kendall (2006), describing them as advanced cognitive abilities that allow students to analyse, reason, experiment, and solve complex scientific problems beyond basic understanding. The study finds that the use of ICT, particularly interactive whiteboards, and activities involving group work and student communication have a positive effect on students' scientific higher-order thinking skills in Finland, while this effect is weaker in China.

Bonacini and Murat (2023) examine the availability of resources for remote learning during the COVID-19 period, showing that insufficient access to ICT substantially widens educational inequalities. Students lacking a computer or internet connection, a quiet study space, or access to online learning platforms face markedly worse outcomes,

including lower PISA mathematics scores and a higher likelihood of grade repetition or early school leaving—particularly in contexts where digital education is more widespread. Moreover, Lin et al. (2024) highlighted the distinction between the behavioural and motivational aspects of ICT engagement. The behavioural aspect of ICT engagement negatively affects digital reading performance, while the motivational aspect shows a positive impact. Meta-cognitive strategies play a significant mediating and moderating role: they enhance the positive effects of ICT interest and autonomy, and mitigate the negative influence of ICT social motivation on digital reading. Overall, ICT engagement in reading appears detrimental at the behavioural level (i.e., frequent ICT use both at and outside school) but beneficial at the motivational level (i.e., ICT interest, autonomy, and competence). Falck et al. (2018) show that computer use at school has heterogeneous effects depending on the type of activity. Using computers to look up ideas and information is positively associated with achievement, whereas using them to practise skills or to process and analyse data is negatively related to performance. These opposite patterns produce an overall null effect. The results suggest that ICT tends to be beneficial when it complements traditional instruction rather than when it replaces it, with stronger positive associations observed in more developed countries. Jeong et al. (2024) focused on the concept of digital capital. The study shows that digital infrastructure alone is insufficient to enhance learning outcomes. Teachers’ ICT competencies are crucial to translating digital resources into educational gains. While software infrastructure in schools positively relates to achievement, students’ digital competence is the strongest predictor of performance, whereas frequent device use for homework shows negative effects. Complementarity between teachers’ ICT integration and students’ digital competence further improves results. The relative importance of each dimension varies across contexts: hardware matters more in less digitally developed countries, while students’ digital competence is key in advanced ones.

Another contribution is provided by Acar (2023) that analyse financial literacy using PISA 2018. The author shows that perceived ICT competence has no direct effect on students’ financial literacy, but operates indirectly through reading literacy. Erdogdu and Erdogdu (2023) conducted stepwise multiple OLS regressions using PISA 2018 data. The results indicate that internet use at home during weekends is positively associated with achievement across all subjects, whereas access to video game consoles shows a small positive relationship with science performance. Beyond ICT, smaller classes, adequate learning materials, and positive school climate contribute to higher outcomes. Similarly, Erdogdu (2022a) explored gender differences in attitudes towards ICT using an ordered logistic regression. Girls show more positive attitudes towards ICT than boys. Students attending private schools display greater interest in ICT than those in public schools. Using ICT outside school for leisure is positively associated with students’ interest in ICT. Moreover, students with higher levels of fear of failure and those in larger classes tend to report a stronger interest in ICT. Erdogdu (2022b) used a longitudinal approach

from wave 2006 to wave 2018. He used an OLS fixed effects approach to remove the constant components over time for each country analysed. In this study, the use of ICT at school shows mixed effects: while both the overall use of ICT and the number of computers available for educational purposes are positively associated with student performance, the presence of Internet-connected computers at school is linked to lower reading scores. Conversely, at home, using ICT for academic purposes has a positive effect on achievement, whereas ICT use for leisure is unrelated to learning outcomes. Moreover, Gómez-García et al. (2021) focused on the use of social networks as a teaching resource among Spanish teachers using PISA 2018 data. The results show an overall low use, which is higher among younger, less experienced, and male teachers.

Finally, only two papers used simple linear regression to conduct studies not related to PISA. The first is Karlsson (2022), who analysed the relationship between computer use and test scores using OLS models with school fixed effects on TIMSS 2011 and 2015 data for Grade 4. Frequent computer use at school is negatively associated with students' performance, with stronger effects among low-achieving pupils. Moderate computer use at home (monthly or weekly) shows a small positive association with achievement, whereas daily use is generally neutral or negative. Girls benefit slightly more than boys from home computer use, but no gender differences are found for school use. Overall, these patterns suggest potential distraction effects when ICT is used excessively at school. The second paper is by Ahn (2020) who carried out a OLS on TIMSS 2015, focusing on the concept of loneliness. The evidence shows that greater use of computers at school for schoolwork - on a daily basis - is associated with lower satisfaction in peer relationships. This negative association is particularly pronounced among students with lower academic performance.

Multilevel regression models Among the associative models, multilevel or hierarchical regressions (HLM) are the most representative group. This outcome is not unexpected, given the inherent hierarchical structure of ILSAs, which necessitates the examination of multiple units of analysis. Data are typically collected at different levels: students, who belong to a class (with aggregated class-level data), which in turn is part of a school (information derived from the principals' questionnaire), located within a specific country (with aggregated national data). This nested structure makes HLM the most appropriate, and consequently the most widely adopted, by scholars (Karakolidis et al., 2022). These models enable researchers to differentiate between variability accountable to differing levels of analysis and to estimate context-specific effects. In practice, HLM have been shown to offer greater statistical accuracy and are better suited to the hierarchical nature of ILSA datasets when compared with OLS.

PISA data are used by 37 papers, with an increasing trend. Xu (2016) is the only one who has produced a paper analysing the PISA 2000 data. He uses a two-level generalised HLM, one for students and one for countries, attempting to identify gender differences in access to resources at home. The results show that daughters generally receive more

social and cultural resources, while sons have more access to technological resources. Gender inequality at the national level affects the distribution of resources. Notten and Kraaykamp (2009) used the same approach as Xu (2016) for the PISA 2006 data. The results suggest that a moderate level of access to ICT at home, namely having one computer and one television, is associated with higher science test scores. However, an increase in the number of such devices corresponds to lower performance, indicating that an excess of media resources may reduce the time and attention devoted to learning. The positive effect of computer ownership remains stable across countries, while the negative impact of multiple televisions is stronger in more developed contexts. Related to these first two studies, Zhong (2011) conduct a three-level HLM (students, schools, and countries) using data from PISA 2003 and 2006. Across countries, higher levels of ICT penetration do not necessarily translate into better student digital skills. Conversely, educational expenditure shows a positive association with digital competence in 2006. At the individual level, home ICT access, socio-economic background, and ICT use history emerge as the strongest predictors, jointly explaining around 70–77% of the within-country variance in self-reported digital skills. Gender differences persist, with boys reporting higher confidence in their digital abilities. Overall, the findings highlight the central role of the family environment and point to the need for schools to mitigate ICT-related inequalities affecting disadvantaged students.

There are three papers based on the 2009 PISA data. Benítez Díaz et al. (2019) use a two-level HLM, student and school, to evaluate activities in the use of ICT. The association between using the internet at home for schoolwork and performance in mathematics is positive, while using it to communicate with classmates and teachers has a negative relationship. Therefore, the authors emphasise the need to work on how the internet is used to improve its impact on academic performance, showing that cognitive and informational use has a positive association and underscoring the relevance of pedagogically structured ICT practices. Conversely, Ma et al. (2019) utilised both HLM and logistic HLM to evaluate the second digital divide, which pertains to the disparity in the utilisation and benefits derived from digital technologies in learning contexts, extending beyond mere access. Finally, Lim and Jung (2019) evaluated the PISA 2009, focusing on digital reading. The study shows that students' digital reading performance is positively associated with effective navigation, metacognitive strategies, favourable attitudes toward ICT, and socially oriented online reading activities. Male students generally outperform females in digital reading, although these associations vary across schools and countries.

There are five papers analysing PISA 2012, all of which analyse mathematics scores from different perspectives. Alagumalai and Buchdahl (2021) focused on gender differences in ICT use on mathematics literacy outcomes. Boys outperform girls in interpreting, employing, and formulating. Furthermore, ICT use in mathematics lessons is negatively associated with all three processes. Eickelmann et al. (2017) evaluated activities using ICT in five countries (Australia, Germany, the Netherlands, Norway and Singapore).

At the level of the school, factors such as leadership and ICT-related strategies play a relevant role in shaping the use of computers in mathematics lessons. However, the impact of these factors on students' mathematics performance differs across countries; in the Netherlands and Germany, the impact is negative, while in Australia, Norway and Singapore it is statistically non-significant. Hew and Tan (2016) show that ICT integration is higher in schools with more computers per student, richer IT resources, clearer curricular expectations for ICT use, and explicit ICT-integration policies in mathematics. Higher levels of integration are also reported by students taught by teachers who endorse student-centred beliefs and implement more problem-solving activities. Meggiolaro (2018) also studied the gender divide in ICT activities. The use of ICT, particularly for gaming and information management, is positively associated with performance in mathematics, showing stronger associations for boys than for girls; however, girls benefit more in specific areas such as content creation and problem solving. Tan and Hew (2017) emphasises the role of ICT availability even in less advantaged family contexts. The results indicate that access to home ICT resources and mother's education positively impact achievement; ICT resource shortages in schools negatively impact achievement. Access to home ICT resources positively influences students' mathematics achievement, with greater benefits for students from less advantaged backgrounds, while students from highly educated families benefit less.

As regards papers using PISA 2015, the starting point is Arpacı et al. (2021). The scholars analyse the situation at country level. In countries with low ICT development, such as those in South America, greater availability and use of ICT improve science performance, whereas in high ICT development countries, such as European countries, the impact of ICT on science performance is diminished, and can even become negative. The variance in performance among European countries cannot be explained by attitudes towards ICT. Gil-Flores and García-Gómez (2017) was based exclusively on the Spanish sample. The results of the study indicate that ESCS is the most significant factor influencing PISA scores in the science domain. Furthermore, it states that students in schools with more computers tend to achieve lower average scores, suggesting that the presence of technology does not inherently guarantee improvements in educational performance. The study by Gómez-Fernández and Mediavilla (2021), based on Spanish PISA 2015 data, finds that students' use of ICT at school and for homework is negatively associated with achievement in mathematics, science, and reading. In contrast, higher ICT interest, moderate leisure use, and better school computer resources are positively related to performance. Quantile analyses indicate that these associations are stronger among low-achieving students. X. Hu et al. (2018) use three-level HLM, focusing first on the country level and then on the meso and micro levels. National ICT skills were positively associated with student achievement across all subjects. ICT availability at school showed a positive relationship with academic performance, whereas ICT availability at home and ICT use for academic purposes were negatively associated with achievement.

Among attitudinal factors, students' interest, perceived competence, and autonomy in using ICT were positively related to performance, while enjoyment of social interaction around ICT showed a negative association. In Juhaňák et al. (2018), the authors analyse a sample of data from the Czech Republic, thereby highlighting a negative relationship between performance and the use of ICT in both school and everyday life contexts. Conversely, the perception of autonomy in ICT use has been demonstrated to be positively associated with test scores. Instead, Juhaňák et al. (2019) aims to identify the optimal age at which children should begin using ICT. Their results suggest that starting to use a computer before the age of six is associated with higher perceived ICT competence and autonomy among fifteen-year-olds. These effects are largely mediated by students' interest in ICT, entertainment-related use, and social interactions involving ICT, whereas the use of ICT at home for schoolwork shows little or no mediating role. Differences between schools explain only a minimal share of the variance. Martínez-Gautier et al. (2021) uses a three-level HLM to analyse the Spanish sample data. The availability and guided educational use of ICT is positively associated with students' academic performance, whereas excessive or recreational use, particularly at home, can hinder learning outcomes. When ICT use becomes daily or more frequent (above +2 standard deviations from the OECD mean), students' performance declines by up to 60 PISA points, equivalent to almost two school years of learning. The last study in this group is M. Wang et al. (2023), who apply a three-level HLM to examine collaborative problem solving (CPS) and social media use. Leisure-related social media activities are positively associated with CPS, while academic uses produce mixed results: interactions with peers are beneficial, whereas interactions with teachers are linked to lower performance. Students who view social media as a useful learning tool also tend to achieve higher CPS scores.

The PISA 2018 wave is the most extensively analysed, with 13 papers focusing on this dataset. Bhutoria and Aljabri (2022) shows how the returns on ICT use are decreasing and therefore follow an inverted U shape. ICT use has a positive impact on student performance up to a moderate threshold (several times a week), beyond which returns diminish. This pattern of decrease in return is stronger in countries with advanced ICT infrastructure, while developing countries still benefit from higher levels of exposure to ICT. A further study by Gimenez and Vargas-Montoya (2021) finds that ICT use during lessons is negatively associated with students' PISA scores, while its interaction with national human capital is positive and significant: in countries with higher human capital, the use of ICT in class improves learning outcomes. Here, human capital is defined as the country-level stock of education and skills embodied in the adult population, capturing both the quantity (average years of schooling, see Barro and Lee (2013)) and the economic return of education (human capital index from the Penn World Table, see Feenstra et al. (2015)). Overall, the findings suggest that the educational effectiveness of ICT depends on the human capital context of each country. Furthermore, Vargas-Montoya et al. (2023) shows that higher use of digital technologies during classroom instruction is significantly

associated with lower student performance in test scores. This negative relationship is stronger in less developed countries and weaker in more developed ones, suggesting that the impact of ICT use on learning outcomes is highly dependent on the national context. Vargas-Montoya et al. (2024) focus their analysis on so-called “gifted” students, i.e. those who perform at the top of the PISA scores. The results show that the use of ICT in school is negatively associated with performance for the general population, but positively and significantly for gifted students. The positive effect increases with performance level, indicating a selective benefit of ICT for high-ability students. Loh et al. (2023) show that digital competences and information-seeking or social uses of ICT are positively associated with performance, whereas gaming is negatively related to achievement. In PISA 2018, simple access to ICT matters far less than how technology is used. These patterns are socially stratified, with high-SES students displaying more advantageous ICT profiles.

The paper by Borgonovi et al. (2023) opens a section dedicated to the role of teachers in the relationship between ICT and academic performance. The authors show that student boredom is associated with teacher enthusiasm, using an HLM for eight countries. The results indicate that higher use of ICT for leisure is associated with increased academic boredom, whereas ICT use for learning at home is linked to reduced boredom. Teacher enthusiasm significantly moderates these associations, consistently lowering students’ likelihood of experiencing boredom. In J. Hu and Wang (2022) students’ perceptions of instruction quality, specifically the adaptation of instruction, stimulation of reading engagement, and a positive disciplinary climate, are positively associated with digital reading performance, whereas teacher-directed instruction, reading skills exercises, teaching of digital skills, and teacher feedback show negative correlations. Xiao and Hew (2022) created a three-level HLM, showing that students’ perceived interest, autonomy, and competence in using ICT are positively correlated with reading performance, while perceived social interaction in using ICT negatively impacts reading performance. School-level support in ICT devices and teachers’ capacity to integrate technology amplifies the positive effects of ICT-related psychological factors and reduces the negative impact of social interaction. As in this latter case, where students’ attitudes towards ICT were carefully analysed, there are other studies that do the same. H. Zhang et al. (2025) focused on students’ perceived confidence in ICT in four countries (China, Germany, Turkey, and Mexico), highlighting that this confidence is positively associated with students’ global competence across countries, possibly because digital tools expand their opportunities to engage with diverse perspectives and global issues. Moreover, the study by Hori and Fujii (2021) shows that the frequent use of ICT for learning purposes, particularly outside of school and linked to schoolwork, significantly enhances both self-efficacy and persistence, while recreational ICT use outside school negatively impacts persistence. The availability of ICT at both home and school has a positive impact on self-efficacy for ICT, although the effect on persistence is less clear. Additionally, ICT use at school has not shown

a significant impact on either self-efficacy or persistence. In line with previous studies, Fayda-Kinik and Cetin (2025) shows through a three-level HLM how positive attitudes towards ICT — in particular interest, perceived competence and perceived autonomy — tend to be associated with higher academic achievement, especially in mathematics and science, while the use of ICT for social interaction generally shows a weak negative relationship with performance. These associations are moderate and more evident among high-achieving students.

Kong et al. (2022) examined gender disparities in the United States, Singapore, and Finland. The results indicate that a positive attitude toward the use of digital devices is associated with higher digital reading achievement, with a stronger effect among male students in the United States and Finland. In contrast, a higher overall frequency of digital device use is negatively associated with digital reading performance. The frequency of reading on digital devices shows a positive association with digital reading achievement, particularly stronger for male students in Singapore. These findings suggest gender differences in how digital use relates to reading outcomes. Overall, they highlight that not all forms of digital engagement contribute equally to learning. Additionally, J. Hu and Hu (2024) corroborates the earlier findings of Juhaňák et al. (2019), highlighting the importance of the age at which students first begin to engage with technology. J. Hu and Hu (2024) found that students who began using digital devices regularly only after age six - particularly between ages seven and twelve - tended to perform worse in digital reading compared to peers who started earlier (0–3 years). The authors also identified cognitive flexibility as a partial mediator of this association: later exposure to regular device use was linked to lower cognitive flexibility, which in turn contributed to poorer digital reading performance.

The last group of papers using PISA data consists of longitudinal studies. Barra and Boccia (2022) analysed PISA waves from 2000 to 2012 across 80 countries, employing a HLM and a quantile regression to show that, among OECD countries, the number of computers is positively associated with student performance, whereas the relationship is not significant for non-OECD countries. D. Zhang and Liu (2016) analysed the same PISA waves as Barra and Boccia (2022), showing that school-level ICT resources have a positive effect on learning outcomes in most PISA cycles, although the effect turns negative in 2012. ICT use for entertainment is generally associated with lower academic performance, except in 2012, when the association becomes slightly positive. Self-confidence in ICT-related tasks consistently predicts better performance in mathematics and science. Courtney et al. (2022) used a three-level HLM for PISA waves from 2009 to 2018. The study demonstrated that the availability and ICT use at home and school were inversely correlated with academic performance in mathematics and science. Attitude is a salient and positive factor, especially with regard to the perception of autonomy in relation to ICT (+9/11 points). Fernández-Gutiérrez et al. (2020) focus on Spanish regions using PISA 2009, 2012, and 2015 data. They find no statistically significant relationship be-

tween the average use of ICT at school and students' performance in mathematics or reading. However, a positive and significant association emerges for science achievement. Results by J. Hu and Yu (2021) show that social media use has mixed but consistent effects on students' digital reading performance across PISA cycles from 2009 until 2018. Recreational activities such as emailing, browsing for fun, and reading online news are positively associated with achievement, whereas online gaming and chatting tend to have negative effects. Academic uses display weaker and often negative associations, particularly when involving communication with teachers. Overall, school-level social media climate shifted from negative to positive between 2009 and 2018, indicating a gradual normalization of digital practices in educational settings.

There is only one paper that uses PISA, TIMSS and PIRLS data together. It is by Skryabin et al. (2015), who analysed the 2012 PISA, 2011 TIMSS and PIRLS waves. The authors used a two-level HLM. The results indicate that the national ICT level is positively and significantly associated with students' achievement in reading, mathematics, and science at all levels of education, even after controlling for countries' economic status. At the individual level, ICT use at home—especially for schoolwork—is positively related to performance, whereas ICT use at school tends to be negatively associated with it.

Three papers use PIRLS data. Netten et al. (2014) analysed the 2001, 2006 and 2011 waves for Dutch students. The results showed that higher computer use at home was negatively related to reading literacy achievement, except for literary texts and higher-order comprehension processes, where the relation was not significant. Gilleece and Eivers (2018) analysed the 2016 wave and found that home Internet access was positively associated with reading performance, suggesting a supportive role of digital connectivity. However, daily computer use for homework and excessive online activity were linked to lower achievement, whereas moderate and purposeful use appeared to foster better outcomes. Moreover, owning a smartphone or having a television in the bedroom showed a small but consistent negative association with reading results. Pongsophon (2024) analysed the 2021 wave for Singapore, Russia, Finland, England, and Hong Kong. Digital self-efficacy was found to have a positive and significant association with reading achievement only in England, while no significant effects were observed in the other countries. Similarly, the availability of school-level ICT resources positively predicts reading outcomes only in the English sample.

Only Saal et al. (2020) used TIMSS data, specifically the 2015 wave for Germany. Frequent use of computers or tablets, both at home and at school, is associated with significantly lower mathematics achievement. In contrast, shared access to devices and home Internet connectivity are positively correlated with performance.

Finally, Aydin (2022) conducted an analysis using ICILS 2018 data for Korea and Finland. Students' ICT use is not uniformly beneficial. Using general applications for learning tasks improves Computer and Information Literacy, while social or entertainment uses reduce it. Positive attitudes and confidence in basic ICT skills support achievement,

but reliance on specialised or non-academic uses does not. Effectiveness depends on how ICT is used, not how often.

Overall, the evidence from HLM studies reveals a highly heterogeneous picture: the effects of ICT depend strongly on context, on how technology is used, and on students' competencies. The findings converge in showing that access alone matters little without structured pedagogical practices, solid digital skills, and balanced, non-excessive use.

Structural equation models The use of structural equation modelling (SEM) with data from ILSAs offers several methodological advantages. The most relevant is that SEM allows researchers to model latent constructs and to account for measurement error and complex interdependencies among observed variables (Bollen, 1989). As a result, this approach has been extensively used to examine the potential relationship between access to ICT or use of ICT and educational performance, considering that there are mediating variables (e.g., attitudes toward ICT, interest in ICT or perceived competence or autonomy in ICT usage) affecting the relationship between the variables of interest and educational outcomes (Rutkowski & Zhou, 2014). This mediational structure allows the authors to explore complex pathways among multiple variables within a single unified model, which is not easily achievable with traditional regression techniques. One of the key advantages of SEM is its ability to represent the relationships - and interrelationships - between latent and observed variables through a system of equations and an associated trajectory diagram. This visual and mathematical formalisation allows researchers to specify, test, and interpret complex theoretical models involving direct and indirect relationships among multiple constructs. Moreover, it is worth noting that the SEM framework can be adapted to accommodate the hierarchical nature of the data from ILSAs by implementing a multilevel structural equation model (ML-SEM), which extends standard SEM to allow for variation at both the individual and school levels.

Liem et al. (2014) conduct one of the earliest studies applying SEM to examine the relationship between ICT use and academic performance. Using data from a sample of students from 25 countries participating in PISA 2003, the study explores how students' engagement with arts-related ICT activities relates to their performance on cognitive tasks. The authors construct a latent variable for arts-related ICT use based on students' self-reports and estimate its direct and indirect effects on digital problem-solving performance and academic achievement. The results show that arts-related ICT use is positively associated with digital problem-solving skills, which in turn are positively linked to academic achievement. Li and Petersen (2022) use data from seven countries participating in PISA 2015 to examine the relationships between students' ICT use and their academic achievement. The authors employ ML-SEM including three variables of ICT use as exogenous predictors (educational use at school, leisure use at school, and educational use at home) and four latent mediators (ICT interest, perceived ICT competence, perceived autonomy, and ICT usage for learning purposes). The results indicate

that ICT use at home for educational purposes has a positive indirect effect on achievement, largely mediated by increased ICT interest and perceived learning usefulness. In contrast, leisure use of ICT at school is associated with negative indirect effects, particularly through lower levels of ICT interest and perceived competence. A very similar approach is also used by Li and Zhu (2023) using PISA 2018 data. The model distinguishes between two types of ICT use (for academic purposes and for leisure), which are modeled as predictors of a construct (cognitive-motivational engagement in ICT) derived from students' interest in ICT, their perceived competence in using digital technologies, and their sense of autonomy when working with ICT. The results show that ICT use for academic purposes is positively associated with cognitive-motivational engagement, while ICT use for leisure has a negative association. Park and Weng (2020) investigate the relationship between ICT-related factors and students' academic achievement across 39 countries, using data from PISA 2015. The main novelty of this study is that it explores the moderating effects of two country-level economic development indicators (the Gini index and GDP per capita) on this relationship. The authors apply a MLSEM approach. The results indicate that ICT academic use and ICT use for entertainment are both negatively associated with students' academic achievement. In contrast, interest in ICT use, perceived competence, and perceived autonomy show positive associations with student performance. Y. Wang and Wang (2023) examine the relationship between educational ICT resources, student engagement, and academic performance using data from PISA 2018. In this study, several indicators of students' engagement with ICT act as mediating variables within an ML-SEM framework used to explain academic performance. The results show that ICT resources at school are positively associated with student engagement, and that engagement, in turn, is a strong positive predictor of academic performance. Other two studies using cross-national data from PISA 2015 and applying ML-SEM are Areepattamannil and Santos (2019) and Chen and Hu (2020), although these studies focus on examining the relationship between students' interest in ICT and their self-perceived competence and autonomy in using these tools. The results of both studies show a consistently positive association between the variables, highlighting the central role of motivational factors in shaping perceived digital competence during adolescence. Joshi et al. (2025) apply SEM on PISA 2022 data to explore the relationship between various frequencies of ICT use and mathematics achievement. Their findings suggest that moderate use of digital tools both outside and at school, as well as during leisure time is positively associated with achievement. However, frequent or excessive use of digital resources for learning content, feedback, or extended screen time is negatively associated with performance.

While the previous studies have primarily relied on cross-country datasets to explore the influence of various ICT-related indicators on academic performance, it is worth noting that the literature also includes research conducted within specific national contexts. For instance, Bulut and Cutumisu (2018) analyze data from PISA 2012 to examine the

relationship between ICT availability and use - both at home and at school - and student performance separately for two countries: Turkey and Finland. The findings highlight substantial cross-country differences since ICT use outside of school for academic purposes was positively associated with math achievement in Turkey, but no significant relationship was found between ICT use and achievement in Finland. Similarly, Odell et al. (2020) also focus on two single countries (Bulgaria and Finland) to examine the relationship between ICT-related factors and science achievement using data from PISA 2015. The authors employ SEM to estimate country-specific models that include three key constructs (ICT availability, ICT use, and ICT comfort) and control for students' SES. The results reveal a consistent pattern in both countries. First, ICT use and ICT availability are negatively associated with science achievement. Second, students who report greater comfort with ICT tend to perform better in science. In another study focused on the specific context of Finland, Saarinen et al. (2021) examine the relationship between ICT availability and ICT use at school and cognitive learning outcomes using PISA 2015 data. As in the previous studies, the application of SEM is not particularly well justified, given that the model does not include mediating variables and does not take full advantage of the capabilities of SEM to capture indirect effects or complex latent constructs. Their findings reveal a negative and statistically significant association between frequent use of digital technologies at school and cognitive performance. Alderete et al. (2017) analyze Spanish data from PISA 2012 to examine the relationship between the use of ICT (at home and at school) and student performance in mathematics and reading with SEM. The authors construct latent variables to capture different dimensions of ICT access and usage, incorporating mediating factors such as students' attitudes toward ICT and their perceived competence. Their results suggest that ICT use at home is positively associated with academic achievement, whereas ICT use at school shows no significant effect or even a slight negative association in some specifications. Similarly, Lang et al. (2024) analyze data from Slovenian students who participated in PISA 2018 to explore the relationship between the daily use of digital technologies and students' reading and information literacy skills relying on a SEM approach. Their model includes four latent constructs that capture students' attitudes and dispositions toward digital technology (enjoyment, self-efficacy, autonomy and independence, and perceived learning with ICT). The results reveal that frequent non-educational use of digital technologies (e.g. for communication or entertainment) is negatively associated with both reading and information literacy. In contrast, positive attitudes toward ICT, particularly enjoyment and perceived learning, are positively associated with both outcomes.

We can also find studies using SEM to explore alternative research questions. For instance, González-Betancor et al. (2021) use data from PISA 2018 in 21 European countries to analyze how the school can act as a compensatory agent in contexts of digital inequality at home. Their estimation strategy is based on a SEM approach that formalizes the relationships between students' SES and three dimensions of ICT integration at

home: access, frequency of use, and quality of use. The empirical results show that SES is a key determinant of ICT access and use at home, and that stronger ICT integration at school is positively associated with students' digital engagement at home. This relationship captures an indirect pathway through which schools may help mitigate digital inequalities, particularly for socioeconomically disadvantaged students. Liu et al. (2024) use data from STEM teachers participating in PISA 2022 to explore the interrelationships between digital professional development, professional learning communities, and the integration of digital tools into classroom instruction. To analyze these relationships, the study employs a Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Model (PLS-SEM), which allows for the simultaneous estimation of direct and indirect effects while addressing potential measurement errors. The latent variables are each measured through multiple-item scales included in the PISA teacher questionnaire. The findings indicate that teachers who frequently engage in digital professional development activities are more likely to collaborate with colleagues and participate in professional learning communities. These communities, in turn, foster a culture of shared practice and mutual support that enhances the integration of digital technologies into STEM instruction. Finally, it is worth noting that many authors employing SEM often refer to the effects of some variables on others, implicitly assuming that this approach allows for the estimation of causal effects. This would require the fulfilment of three conditions: the existence of an empirical association, the correct specification of the direction of the relationship, and the isolation of the effect from potential confounding factors. However, this last requirement is particularly difficult to achieve when working with cross-sectional data because the relationship between those variables may be influenced by unobserved factors (e.g., prior student ability, family support, or teacher quality) that simultaneously affect both explanatory variables and learning outcomes. Therefore, while SEM is a valuable tool for exploring complex associations, interpretations derived from these analysis cannot be assumed as causal.

Machine Learning The present group consists of papers that have employed a machine learning (ML) technique to analyse ILSA data. Among the various ML techniques suitable for knowledge discovery, clustering methods are widely used when working with large volumes of data. Clustering is a fundamental task in data mining that groups observations according to their similarities, synthesizing the information in the data and thus making it more accessible. Nonetheless, clustering results also depend on the data quality, and their interpretability can be particularly challenging due to the unsupervised nature of the problem.

The study by Alvarez-Garcia, Arenas-Parra, and Ibar-Alonso (2024) analyses data from the Spanish PISA 2022 sample to identify student learning profiles through an explainable cluster analysis approach. The authors apply Sparse Principal Component Analysis (SPCA) and Multiple Correspondence Analysis (MCA) for dimensionality reduction, followed by a weighted k-means clustering and a classification model based on

XGBoost. Model interpretability is ensured through SHAP (SHapley Additive exPlanations), which quantifies the relative importance of each variable in determining cluster membership. The results show that ICT availability and use at home play a far more decisive role than school-based ICT variables in differentiating student groups. Students with greater home ICT access and higher SES display better academic performance and well-being, whereas those with limited digital access and lower SES show poorer outcomes. The paper concludes that ICT acts as a structural amplifier of educational inequality, rather than an equalising factor.

The study by J. Hu et al. (2023) found that ICT-related factors, SES, and educational resources are significant predictors of digital reading performance. This conclusion emerges from Support Vector Machine models interpreted through SHAP analysis. High-performing students demonstrate a more intentional and learning-oriented approach to ICT. They spend more time reading emails and searching for information online, displaying greater autonomy and interest in technology. They also benefit from teachers who explicitly integrate digital literacy into their lessons, for example by teaching to recognise biased information, interpret search results and understand the consequences of sharing content online, for example. In contrast, low-performing students tend to use ICT for generic or social purposes, such as chatting and participating in forums. They demonstrate a lack of interest in technology and are more exposed to ICT misuse, classroom disorder and discrimination at school. All of these factors are negatively associated with digital reading achievement. Rico-Juan et al. (2024) applied CatBoost, a non-linear gradient boosting algorithm based on decision trees and iterative optimisation, to Spanish data from PISA 2018. The study reports significant associations between ICT-related variables and reading performance. Frequent online gaming shows a negative association with reading scores, whereas Internet use on weekdays exhibits an inverted U-shaped relationship: moderate use (between one and four hours per day) is linked to higher performance compared to both no use and excessive use. Perceived ICT competence and autonomy display strong positive relationships, with average gaps of about +30 and +50 PISA points, respectively, between the lowest and highest levels. Consistent with the results, early exposure to digital devices during preschool years appears to foster interest in reading comprehension and cognitive development, whereas later exposure, from around age nine, may hinder adaptation to digital environments and negatively affect reading literacy. Gender differences are also observed, with females outperforming males in reading comprehension.

Silva et al. (2024) investigates the factors influencing students' educational use of digital technologies using data from PISA 2018. The study applies a ML decision tree approach to identify the main determinants of ICT use for learning purposes. The results show that access to ICT at school and at home, along with balanced recreational use, autonomy, and digital competence, positively affects students' educational engagement with technology. When teacher-related variables are included, job satisfaction and ped-

agogical use of ICT emerge as positive predictors, while lack of ICT training negatively influences outcomes. The study concludes that effective educational use of ICT depends on the interplay between digital resources, individual skills, and teachers' instructional practices.

The ML literature reveals that ICT-related indicators, SES, and digital competence jointly determine students' digital engagement profiles. Non-linear patterns emerge across studies: information-seeking and autonomy tend to align with stronger performance, whereas gaming and unstructured use are negatively associated. The findings highlight the value of ML approaches in identifying diverse behavioural patterns.

Hybrid approaches The hybrid papers integrate more than one methodological approach within the same analysis. Typically, these studies first classify or structure the data through techniques such as Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) or Latent Class/Latent Profile Analysis (LCA/LPA), and subsequently perform regression analyses on the resulting groups or factors (Costa & Chen, 2023; Gil-Flores et al., 2012; Wittwer & Senkbeil, 2008). Other contributions combine traditional statistical modelling with ML techniques, for instance by integrating Random Forest models (RF) with HLM (Lezhnina & Kismihók, 2022; Peng et al., 2023). As noted by Lezhnina and Kismihók (2022), the flexible way to combine statistical and machine learning approaches can be recommended to educational researchers, since in our age of growing data volumes and complexity, creative adaptability and methodological versatility are indispensable.

The first two hybrid studies, Pitzalis and Porcu (2024) and M. Kim and Kim (2023), are quite similar in that they employ latent analysis without subsequently performing regression models. Pitzalis and Porcu (2024) use Italian data from PISA 2018 to explore the relationship between cultural and digital capital through a LPA. The analysis identifies four student profiles, mainly differentiated by economic and cultural capital. ICT-related indicators do not emerge as an autonomous dimension of cultural capital but are instead intertwined with SES and gender differences, with male students showing more intensive use. Reading and mathematics results remain strongly associated with cultural capital, while the digital component shows only a weak and non-discriminating relationship with academic performance or school choice. M. Kim and Kim (2023) performed a LCA. The results indicate that, in high-performing countries, student groups characterised by high perceived autonomy in ICT use but low levels of school-based ICT use achieved the highest reading literacy, whereas those with the strongest overall ICT familiarity showed the lowest reading literacy. Moreover, greater ICT familiarity was associated with a higher proportion of male students and higher SES, suggesting that limited ICT familiarity corresponds to lower SES, while greater ICT engagement is more prevalent among male students.

Gil-Flores et al. (2012) investigate the relationship between internet use and students' digital reading performance in Spain, using data from PISA 2009. A Categorical Prin-

Principal Components Analysis (CATPCA) was applied to seven online activity items to identify two distinct dimensions of Internet use: information-seeking (such as reading news, consulting online dictionaries, and searching for information) and social (chatting and emailing). These components were then included in multiple linear regression models to explain students' reading performance. The results show that information-seeking activities have a positive and statistically significant association with digital reading scores, while social activities have a much weaker effect. When traditional reading ability is controlled for, the effect of ICT use decreases but remains significant, suggesting that using the Internet to seek information slightly improves digital reading performance, whereas social use does not contribute meaningfully. In their study based on PISA 2012 data from Scandinavian countries, Costa and Chen (2023) applied a three-factor CFA to describe the latent dimensions of students' behaviour in computer-based mathematics tasks. The three identified factors represent Performance (response accuracy), Speed (log-transformed response time), and Exploration behaviour (log-transformed number of actions). The authors then estimated a latent regression model to examine the relationship between these factors and a composite ICT factor, together with background variables. The results show that ICT availability and use are negatively associated with mathematics performance only in Denmark, while no significant effects are found in Sweden or Norway. Wittwer and Senkbeil (2008) use data from PISA 2003 in Germany to examine the relationship between ICT use and mathematics performance. A LCA of 18 ICT items identified four user profiles: smart, rational, recreational and indifferent. These profiles were included as predictors in multiple regression models controlling for SES, gender, migration status, cognitive ability and leisure activities. The results show that neither computer availability nor frequency of use at home are positively related to mathematics performance once controls are applied. Only autodidactic smart users, who learn independently and use technology strategically, achieve higher scores in both mathematics and problem solving. In addition, Gubbels et al. (2020) analyse the Dutch PISA 2015 sample to examine how access to, use of, and attitudes toward ICT relate to digitally assessed reading performance. They applied a CFA followed by multiple linear regression. Their findings reveal a threshold effect, indicating an inverted U-shaped relationship: moderate access to and use of ICT resources are positively associated with digital reading performance, whereas excessive access, use, and interest in ICT are negatively associated with it.

Two papers combined HLM and ML approaches. Peng et al. (2023) draw on PISA 2018 data to PISA 2018. The authors conducted a CFA to construct school-level latent variables, and then combined a RF model and a three-level HLM to examine the relationship between ICT-related factors and students' reading performance. The study finds that ICT-related factors have heterogeneous effects on reading performance. Students' perceived autonomy and competence in ICT, as well as their preference for different reading formats, are positively associated with achievement. The quality of school ICT resources

and institutional ICT policies also contribute positively. However, interest in ICT, home ICT resources, and ICT use for entertainment or schoolwork show an inverted U-shaped relationship, suggesting benefits only at moderate levels. School support for teachers and direct teaching of ICT skills are negatively related to performance, interpreted by the authors as evidence of weak pedagogical integration: schools may prioritise technical assistance and basic ICT training rather than instructional use, leading to inefficient or even counterproductive effects. Overall, ICT appears to enhance learning when it is purposefully integrated and used in balanced ways. Similarly, Lezhnina and Kismihók (2022) combine a RF classifier with HLM models to analyse the relationship between students' attitudes toward ICT and their performance in mathematics and science, using the German samples of PISA 2015 and 2018. The RF model is applied to classify students into proficiency levels and to identify the most relevant predictors, followed by HLM assessing associations with PISA scores. The results show that autonomy in ICT use is positively associated with achievement, while ICT use for social interaction is negatively associated. The perceived ICT competence and the interest show no significant relationships. In both models, SES remains the strongest determinant of student performance.

Borgonovi and Pokropek (2021) analyse PISA data from 2009 to 2018 across 28 countries to examine trends and outcomes of students' ICT use. Three indices - ICT for fun, learning at home, and learning at school - were built using CFA with alignment optimisation to ensure cross-country comparability, and analysed through linear regressions with country fixed effects and polynomial and piecewise specifications. The use of ICT rose markedly with time, especially for learning, while reading performance remained stable. Boys increased the use of ICT for fun and school work more than girls. The results revealed an inverted U-shaped relationship between ICT use and reading: moderate use was beneficial, whereas excessive use (for both fun and learning) correlated with lower achievement, a pattern that intensified over time.

H. Kim et al. (2021) first apply a LPA and then a multinomial logistic regression to PISA 2018 data. The results show that the schools with higher SES and private management are significantly more likely to exhibit higher levels of digital inclusion, as reflected in stronger digital infrastructure, greater institutional support for technology integration, and higher teacher and student digital literacy. Finally, Hahnel et al. (2023) identifies three distinct patterns of behaviour in ICT-based digital reading tasks: on-task, exploring, and disengaged. Students showing on-task or exploring behaviour achieve higher digital reading performance, invest more appropriate processing time, and navigate more precisely across hypertext pages. Disengaged students, by contrast, display minimal interaction and significantly lower outcomes. Socio-economic disparities and lower print reading skills increase the likelihood of disengaged or inefficient use patterns. The findings suggest that educational use of ICT is shaped by students' prior competences and socio-cultural background, with implications for digital equity and instructional design.

Overall, these studies reveal a trend towards methodological hybridisation, seeking

to combine the robustness of latent or predictive models with the explanatory power of regression analysis, enabling richer and more nuanced insights.

3.2.2 Causal analysis

The second strand of the analysed literature consists of causal studies. Although ILSAs were not originally intended to support causal inference, researchers have increasingly adapted these datasets to address policy-relevant questions. Drawing on their extensive background information and broad international coverage, a growing body of literature shows that, despite certain methodological limitations, ILSAs can yield valuable insights into the causal mechanisms underlying educational outcomes. This is exemplified by the following studies, which leverage ILSA data to examine the impact of ICT on a variety of educational outcomes, applying quasi-experimental methods to strengthen the validity of their findings.

The first study, by De Witte and Rogge (2014), examines the impact of ICT availability and use on student achievement in mathematics using data from TIMSS 2011 for Dutch fourth-grade students. To address selection bias, the authors employ a Mahalanobis distance matching procedure to construct equivalent control and treatment groups based on a rich set of student-, teacher-, school-, and regional-level covariates. Their findings indicate that ICT availability and frequency of use do not have a statistically significant effect on student performance in mathematics. Using a matching-based approach as well, but employing a different technique (Propensity Score Matching - PSM) to address selection bias, Agasisti et al. (2020) investigate the relationship between students' use of ICT at home for school-related tasks and their academic performance using PISA 2012. Shifting the focus to secondary education and expanding the sample to include twelve EU countries, they find a generally negative association between intensive ICT use at home and student achievement across all assessed competencies, a pattern that holds for both low- and high-performing students. With a specific focus on reading literacy, Rosén and Gustafsson (2016) analyse how computer use at home affects reading achievement among fourth-grade students using data from PIRLS 2001 and 2006. The study, which includes 16 OECD countries, applies a difference-in-differences approach to identify a consistent negative effect of frequent home computer use on reading performance. This effect seems to be partially mediated by a reduction in traditional literacy activities, such as borrowing books. The same competence is also the focus of Fariña et al. (2015), who examine the role of computer use for reading activities using PISA 2009 data for students in Chile, Portugal, Spain, and Uruguay. To address potential endogeneity in students' self-selected use of ICT, particularly at home, the authors employ a two-stage regression model validated by Hausman tests. Their findings reveal that, once endogeneity is accounted for, computer use for reading has no significant positive effect on either digital or traditional reading performance, and in some cases, the association is even negative.

Using PISA 2018 data from Spain, Estonia, and Finland, Gorjón and Osés (2023) explore how the intensity of ICT use at school relates to students' mathematics achievement. Through HLM, they identify an inverted U-shaped relationship, with moderate users outperforming both low and very intensive users. To estimate causal effects, the authors apply Inverse Probability Weighting based on propensity score logits (following DuGoff et al., 2014). The results show that very intensive ICT use leads to substantially lower mathematics scores (around 26–33 points less). Activity-level analyses indicate that excessive use of ICT for classroom tasks is generally detrimental, whereas browsing the internet for schoolwork shows a positive association.

Some works in the recent literature have proposed that the use of machine learning techniques may contribute to this purpose (Athey & Imbens, 2017, 2019; Brand et al., 2023; Chernozhukov et al., 2024; Mullainathan & Spiess, 2017; Wager & Athey, 2018). These methods are based on developing computationally efficient prediction algorithms and addressing the trade-off between bias and variance to achieve high predictive accuracy. The predictions can be made with a multitude of alternative approaches or algorithms (Varian, 2014), such as models based on regression trees, random forest, boosting, artificial neural networks, or Bayesian additive regression trees (BART). Unlike traditional statistics, these techniques are data-driven, thus they do not rely on strong assumptions about data distribution and a prior hypothesized relations between variables. Moreover, they allow the incorporation of a large number of control variables in the analyses that have previously been validated as relevant by the algorithm itself, thus reducing the possible bias that could exist in the estimates due to the non-observation of determinants at a value close to zero (Huber, 2023).

These approaches have enormous potential for estimating causal effects as a problem of prediction of counterfactual values based on the observed covariates ensure that estimates have adjusted for any relevant differences across control and treated groups. Following this idea, Cabras and Tena Horrillo (2016) and Ferraro (2018) examined the influence of using a computer, laptop or tablet at school in the school on the academic performance of students in Spain and Italy, respectively, using PISA 2012 data. Both studies rely on the same method (BART) in their attempt to identify a causal effect for this factor conditional on the other relevant variables introduced in the model and considering their potential interactions. They also coincide in the identification of a positive effect for the variable studied, which is much higher for students from low SES. Veselkova (2024) also used a BART model to examine the relationship between computer (or tablets) availability and academic achievement using data from Slovak students participating in TIMSS and PIRLS. In addition, this study also applies propensity score matching to control for the potential bias in the estimates due to the presence of confounding factors in data. In contrast to the studies mentioned above, this study found that having computers available during their lessons has no impact on student performance when considering the total sample analysed, but a positive effect is identified for certain groups, such as

disadvantaged students or children who never spoke the language of the test at home.

3.2.3 Efficiency analysis

The third and final methodological strand in the literature deals with efficiency analysis. In contrast to all previous studies analyzing the relationship between ICT and student achievement, Mergoni et al. (2023) how ICT influences school efficiency, i.e., the ability of schools to transform the resources they have at their disposal into student outcomes compared to other schools. To do this, they first estimate a measure of school efficiency using a non-parametric frontier approach known as network DEA (Färe et al., 2007). This method allows them to model the education production function as a two-stage process in which the use of ICT for instructional purposes is considered jointly with other input variables like the teacher-student ratio and the computer-student ratio for maximizing student achievement. Likewise, their empirical analysis is complemented by including some contextual factors that might be relevant for the transformation process that takes place in schools adopting a conditional approach. The main findings of this study, which relies on data from 23 European countries obtained through OECD-PISA with a similar structure in terms of ICT equipment, is that the process of transforming ICT instructional time into student learning is the major source of inefficiency. This result could mean that instructors' use of ICT in the classroom explains more than ICT infrastructure.

Feliciano et al. (2021) also use frontier techniques to evaluate the impact of the most ambitious ICT program developed in Spain, the so-called “Escuela 2.0”, with the purpose of improving the availability of laptops in schools. Specifically, they follow the essence of the difference-in-differences analysis comparing the performance of students participating in PISA 2009, when the program has not started yet, and in PISA 2015 when the implementation was already complete. The proposed measures of performance are calculated using the base-group Malmquist index proposed by Aparicio and Santín (2018) and they are based on differences in productivity between schools belonging to regions that implemented the program (treated) and those belonging to regions that did not (control). The results of this study suggest that the program had a negative effect on the productivity levels of schools for all the regions that implemented this program.

3.3 Findings: the classification of ICT

We group the findings from this substantial body of research into three categories to enhance interpretability. This typology, informed by the existing literature, acknowledges the multidimensional nature of ICT-related constructs, as well as the absence of a single, widely accepted classification. Despite this heterogeneity, most studies converge on three broad analytical domains: ICT access and availability; ICT use and frequency of use; and students' engagement with ICT. Adopting this framework allows for a clearer synthesis of results by distinguishing variables that capture complementary yet conceptually distinct

aspects of ICT in education.

ICT access and availability Access to and availability of ICT refers to the physical and infrastructural availability of digital technologies, such as access to devices (computers, tablets, smartphones) and Internet connectivity both at school and at home (International Telecommunication Union, 2015). This dimension represents the fundamental enabling condition for the subsequent domains of ICT use and ICT engagement, since insufficient resources impose a direct constraint on any form of technology-mediated learning. For this reason, both the International Telecommunication Union (International Telecommunication Union, 2015), EU (European Commission, 2013) and PISA (OECD, 2003) have emphasised the relevance of this aspect since the early development of the field. Since the early 2000s, research has largely focused on documenting the presence and distribution of technological resources in educational settings. In current times, however, this aspect plays a less central role in the debate. The discussion has progressively shifted towards qualitative aspects, such as how technologies are used and the extent to which students are cognitively and motivationally engaged with ICT. This evolution reflects two main developments: the realisation that infrastructure alone is insufficient to influence learning processes and the significant policy initiatives, both at a national and EU level, that have considerably increased the provision of ICT over the past two decades, resulting in almost universal access to basic technological infrastructure across the EU (X. Hu et al., 2018; International Telecommunication Union, 2015; Skryabin et al., 2015). On average, internet access in EU member states in 2023 was above 90%, with rural areas having come very close to urban areas in recent years (Eurostat, 2024). This data indicates that European development policies have led to an exponential increase in ICT resources. This development has not been equally productive in developing countries, where even today there is literature that emphasises this first dimension. The development of ICT at the national level has a direct influence on education (Skryabin et al., 2015), but also on the national economy in general (Luu & Freeman, 2011). In this regard, before dwelling on some relevant findings, it is important to note a three-point summary of the findings highlighted in the literature:

1. The national level of ICT development plays a fundamental and positive role in shaping ICT availability and academic outcomes.
2. Developing countries are characterised by more limited access to ICT compared to developed nations.
3. The mere presence of ICT is not sufficient to generate clear and positive effects on education.

Skryabin et al. (2015) examine the role of national ICT development and find that countries with higher ICT development levels exhibit better student performance in reading, mathematics, and science, even after controlling for national economic conditions.

Drawing on Cronin (2002), the authors argue that these differences can be understood through the lens of the digital divide, which highlights how unequal access to ICT and related skills contributes to achievement gaps.

This perspective is also supported by the findings of Barra and Boccia (2022), Bhutoria and Aljabri (2022), and Arpacı et al. (2021). Barra and Boccia (2022) and Bhutoria and Aljabri (2022) emphasise the central role played by technology shortages in developing countries. In contexts where ICT infrastructure is more advanced, the marginal returns of ICT on student performance tend to diminish. Europe, for example, has largely achieved widespread access to ICT, unlike many less developed regions. In these settings, the scarcity of ICT resources constrains students' opportunities to use technology and to develop positive attitudes towards it. Students from poorer backgrounds are particularly affected, experiencing limited access to ICT compared to their more affluent peers. This generates a strong correlation between SES and ICT accessibility (Alvarez-Garcia, Arenas-Parra, & Ibar-Alonso, 2024; Cabras & Tena Horrillo, 2016; Giambona & Porcu, 2015; H. Kim et al., 2021; Loh et al., 2023; Tan & Hew, 2017; Zhong, 2011). The evidence provided by X. Hu et al. (2018) confirms this line of interpretation. The authors show that country-level ICT development has a clear and significant impact on student performance. Building on the framework proposed by the ITU, they construct an ICT Development Index that aggregates three components: ICT access, ICT use, and ICT skills (International Telecommunication Union, 2015). This index is then used to assess digital divides both across and within countries (Ghobadi & Ghobadi, 2013). Their results indicate that, in developed countries, the role of access has diminished, as ICT availability has become widespread across the population. What remains decisive are ICT skills, which appear to outweigh the second dimension, namely ICT use. In this sense, the quantity of ICT (its access and availability) emerges as necessary but not sufficient. Instead, the quality of ICT engagement, including the ability of teachers and students to use technology effectively, plays a central role. Consistent with this, the effects of ICT availability differ across contexts: they tend to be negative in the home environment and null at the school level.

Evidence on ICT availability shows a combination of negative and positive associations with student achievement. On the negative side, several studies highlight that greater access to ICT does not necessarily translate into better outcomes. Regarding the home environment, Costa and Chen (2023) and Lee and Wu (2013) report adverse effects of ICT availability, and Notten and Kraaykamp (2009) find that having more than one television or more than one computer at home is negatively related to student performance. At the school level, the evidence similarly points to negative relationships. Several studies document that the ICT resources available in schools are associated with lower achievement Alderete et al. (2017), Odell et al. (2020), and Saarinen et al. (2021). In addition, Gil-Flores and García-Gómez (2017) show that a higher number of computers per classroom is related to lower science competence. In parallel, other contributions doc-

ument positive associations between ICT availability and student outcomes. For OECD countries, Barra and Boccia (2022) find beneficial effects of ICT resources on educational performance. During the COVID-19 period, Bonacini and Murat (2023) and Giambona and Porcu (2015) show that having a computer and an internet connection at home for schoolwork is associated with better educational outcomes, while the lack of such resources is linked to substantial educational inequalities. Similarly, Erdogdu (2022a) and Alderete et al. (2017) report positive relationships between availability of ICT at home and student achievement, and Bulut and Cutumisu (2018) identify favourable effects of ICT access both at home and at school. Focusing on school-level resources, Cabras and Tena Horrillo (2016) find that ICT investment has a moderate positive effect on mathematics scores, with particularly pronounced benefits for students from low SES, while Jeong et al. (2024) document positive associations between software infrastructure in schools and student achievement. Additional evidence of favourable links between ICT availability and student outcomes is provided by Gómez-Fernández and Mediavilla (2021) and Hori and Fujii (2021). One of the earliest studies in this area also highlights a potential gender-related source of inequality: sons tend to have greater access to technological resources than daughters (Xu, 2016). This form of disparity will be discussed in greater detail in the section dedicated to inequalities.

In summary, the evidence on ICT availability is mixed. A larger share of studies suggests positive effects when access supports students from disadvantaged SES, indicating a compensatory role of technology in skill development. However, ICT availability remains a necessary but not sufficient condition for improving learning outcomes: without considering ICT use and engagement, its educational impact is limited. In contexts such as Europe, where access to ICT is already widespread, the key question is whether it helps disadvantaged students to close the gap or contributes to widening performance differences.

ICT use Studies differ in how they conceptualise ICT use, considering aspects such as location (school or out of school), purpose (schoolwork or leisure), and the type of activity, including gaming, communication, online search, collaboration, and social media. Furthermore, the findings frequently consider the differentiated effects across subjects (e.g. mathematics, reading and science). Another key element is the frequency of use, which has become increasingly central to the debate and has stimulated discussion around usage thresholds. This line of research points to a potential inverted U-shaped relationship between ICT use and academic performance.

The 92 studies classified under the ICT use dimension serve as the primary inquiry axis, providing evidence on the relationship between ICT and student achievement. It is evident that not all contributions are exclusively focused on ICT use, but it is notable that several intersect with issues of access and attitudes. The debate has been divided into distinguishable phases. Before 2010, early contributions were coconcentrated mainly

location and purpose. Subsequent analyses have increasingly concentrated on specific activities and, crucially, the role of frequency. The results can be organised around two main recurrent evidences:

1. The literature does not converge on a single unequivocal effect of ICT use on student performance, but rather documents predominantly mixed evidence.
2. The relationship between the amount of ICT use and student outcomes is frequently characterised by an inverted U-shaped pattern: beyond a certain threshold, additional ICT use is associated with lower performance, broadly across activities.

A substantial body of work identifies positive associations between ICT use and student performance, either overall or for specific practices. Several studies highlight the benefits of computer use at home, particularly when compared with use at school (Giambona & Porcu, 2015; Gil-Flores et al., 2012; Kubiato & Vlckova, 2010; Spiezia, 2010). Positive effects also emerge when ICT is used specifically for educational purposes, such as completing schoolwork or searching for academic information (Giambona & Porcu, 2015; Kubiato & Vlckova, 2010; Steffens, 2014). In this direction, “smart users”, students who use ICT in more versatile and academically oriented ways, tend to be more motivated and achieve higher scores (Wittwer & Senkbeil, 2008). Other studies find positive effects for gaming in certain contexts (Biagi & Loi, 2013) and for time spent on the internet at home during a typical weekday (Erdogdu, 2022a). Evidence from school settings also points to benefits: ICT use at school can improve mathematics performance (Ferraro, 2018), and has positive effects in science in contrast with the other domains, according to Fernández-Gutiérrez et al. (2020). Activities involving online information seeking, such as browsing the internet for school-related research, also yield favourable results (Benítez Díaz et al., 2019; Gil-Flores et al., 2012). Similarly, using computers as learning tools (for exploring principles or practising skills) appears more beneficial than using them merely as information tools (for looking up information and processing data) (Kadijevich, 2015). Some contributions emphasise the value of high-quality, domain-specific ICT engagement, such as arts-related ICT use (Liem et al., 2014), or ICT used consistently for educational tasks (Silva et al., 2024). Positive effects also emerge from activities like gaming and information-management practices (Meggiolaro, 2018), moderate computer use at home, and internet use directly tied to schoolwork (Steffens, 2014). Complementary evidence suggests that ICT can enhance learning when integrated as a support tool—for instance, when used to search for ideas and information rather than to replace instruction (Falck et al., 2018). Finally, the shared use of digital resources in the classroom, such as computers or tablets combined with internet connections, can support achievement (Saal et al., 2020).

A considerable share of studies reports negative associations, pointing to risks linked to excessive or misdirected ICT use. This includes intensive use for communication with

peers and teachers (Benítez Díaz et al., 2019), ICT use for learning at school (Vargas-Montoya et al., 2023), and leisure-focused activities, which are associated with increased academic boredom (Borgonovi et al., 2023). High amounts of home computer use are frequently linked to lower performance (Netten et al., 2014; Rosén & Gustafsson, 2016). ICT use during lessons is often negatively associated with outcomes (Gimenez & Vargas-Montoya, 2021), with effects particularly pronounced among low-performing students (Karlsson, 2022). Excessive use of social networks and online gaming also correlates negatively with achievement (Navarro-Martinez & Peña-Acuña, 2022), as does the use of video-game consoles at home (Steffens, 2014). Overuse of digital devices for non-academic purposes outside school undermines reading performance, especially activities such as playing online games and uploading self-created content (Vázquez-Cano et al., 2020). Leisure-driven computer use is again highlighted as detrimental by Wittwer and Senkbeil (2008). Some studies further point to negative effects from using ICT to engage in skill-practice exercises (Falck et al., 2018) or from computer-based reading activities (Fariña et al., 2015). Subject-specific patterns also emerge: frequent computer use in mathematics lessons is associated with poorer outcomes in some countries (Eickelmann et al., 2017), and broad, intensive ICT use across locations (home, school and other places) is linked to lower mathematics scores (Saal et al., 2020). Additional negative associations concern the use of PC for school-related activities (Feliciano et al., 2021), intensive ICT use at home (Agasisti et al., 2020), ICT use during mathematics instruction (Alagumalai & Buchdahl, 2021), and the effect of home computer use on reading achievement (Rosén & Gustafsson, 2016).

The mixed findings may reflect the underlying assumption that the relationship between students' ICT use and achievement is linear (Rodrigues & Biagi, 2017). Within this heterogeneous evidence, one of the most consistent findings concerns the frequency of ICT use. A growing number of studies shows that the relationship between ICT use and academic performance often follows an inverted U-shaped pattern, where moderate levels of use are associated with the highest performance (Borgonovi & Pokropek, 2021; Fernández-Gutiérrez et al., 2020; Gorjón & Osés, 2023; Gubbels et al., 2020; Li & Zhu, 2023; Martínez-Gautier et al., 2021; Peng et al., 2023; Rico-Juan et al., 2024; Steffens, 2014). Related contributions discuss specific thresholds beyond which ICT use becomes counterproductive (Bhutoria & Aljabri, 2022; Karlsson, 2022; Liem et al., 2014; Saarinen et al., 2021). The broader message is consistent: moderate use tends to be beneficial, whereas both minimal and excessive use correlate with weaker outcomes. For example, Borgonovi and Pokropek (2021) show that excessive ICT use, whether for learning or for leisure, is increasingly associated with lower reading performance. Similarly, several studies highlight concrete thresholds, such as more than six hours of daily use (Rozgonjuk et al., 2021), or intermediate ranges (e.g. one to four hours) as potentially optimal (Joshi et al., 2025; Rico-Juan et al., 2024). A similar non-linear relationship was found between ICT use and reading performance in the Dutch sample (Gubbels et al., 2020).

Some contributions have emphasised the significance of the first age of ICT usage in shaping students' digital proficiency and academic performance. J. Hu and Hu (2024) provides one of the most detailed analyses of this dimension. The study shows that early and regular access to digital devices, especially between ages 4 and 6, is associated with neutral or even positive digital reading outcomes. In contrast, first exposure that begins between ages 7 and 12 is linked to progressively more negative associations in many countries. Very late access, after age 13, as well as the absence of access altogether, is consistently related to lower digital reading performance across contexts. Similarly, Juhaňák et al. (2019) report that initiating ICT use after age 6 is associated with significantly lower levels of ICT competence and autonomy. Rico-Juan et al. (2024) reports that reading outcomes are higher when children first use digital devices before age 10, while later introduction is linked to progressively lower performance. Gómez-Fernández and Mediavilla (2021) and Navarro-Martinez and Peña-Acuña (2022) also finds a negative relationship between ICT exposure and PISA results, although without identifying a clear age threshold. In contemporary societies, early exposure to digital tools has become unavoidable. Nonetheless, defining when and to what extent ICT should be introduced in childhood remains a key policy question (Casillas Martín et al., 2020). The timing of first exposure has implications not only for cognitive and psychological development, but also for long-term human capital formation and economic growth.

ICT Engagement ICT Engagement represents the final dimension in our framework and captures students' general disposition towards ICT. This construct comprises four main components: *ICT interest*, referring to the motivational tendency to engage with ICT-related topics and activities; *perceived ICT competence*, that is, students' beliefs about their own ability to use ICT effectively; *perceived autonomy in ICT use*, understood as a sense of control and self-direction in ICT-related activities; and *ICT as a topic in social interaction*, which reflects the extent to which ICT features in exchanges with others and thereby supports informal learning. This cognitive-motivational aspect of ICT literacy was first introduced by Zylka et al. (2015), drawing on self-determination theory (Deci & Ryan, 2000), and subsequently refined by Goldhammer et al. (2016). ICT Engagement is thus conceived as a key individual factor enabling the self-regulated development and updating of digital skills over the life course in both formal and informal learning environments (Kunina-Habenicht & Goldhammer, 2020).

Within our review, 51 studies examine at least one aspect of ICT Engagement. Most contributions do not focus exclusively on this dimension, but instead combine it with elements of ICT access and ICT use. Nonetheless, the evidence in this area is particularly informative, as ICT Engagement plausibly operates as a mediating mechanism through which ICT use can translate into improved student outcomes. The empirical findings can be summarised in three main points:

1. Most studies document a positive association between ICT engagement and student

achievement.

2. ICT engagement frequently acts as a mediating mechanism linking ICT use to student outcomes, helping to explain otherwise mixed results.
3. All components of ICT engagement matter, although perceived autonomy in ICT often appears particularly salient.

The large majority of studies document a positive association between ICT engagement and student achievement. Perceived ICT competence is positively related to a range of outcomes, including performance in mathematics and science (D. Zhang & Liu, 2016), financial literacy (Acar, 2023) and global competence (H. Zhang et al., 2025). Higher ICT self-efficacy and confidence in ICT use are linked to more frequent engagement with digital tools (Güzeller & Akin, 2014; Tømte & Hatlevik, 2011) and, more generally, to better academic results (Fayda-Kinik & Cetin, 2025; Kong et al., 2022; Odell et al., 2020; Petko et al., 2017). A similar pattern emerges for broader digital competence and self-efficacy, which tend to support higher achievement (Gómez-Fernández & Mediavilla, 2021; Jeong et al., 2024; Pongsophon, 2024). Several contributions show that motivational components such as interest, autonomy and perceived competence are positively associated with reading performance (Lee & Wu, 2012, 2013; Lin et al., 2024; Xiao & Hew, 2022), science outcomes (Odell et al., 2020), or achievement more generally (Li & Petersen, 2022; Park & Weng, 2020). In some cases, autonomy appears particularly important: for example, students' autonomy in ICT use exerts a stronger influence on their scientific dispositions than perceived competence (Arepattamannil & Santos, 2019), and classes characterised by high perceived autonomy combined with relatively low ICT use at school display the highest reading scores in high-performing countries (M. Kim & Kim, 2023). Other studies report that ICT autonomy is positively associated with mathematics and science achievement, whereas ICT use for social interaction is negatively related to performance, while interest and perceived competence are not significantly associated with test scores (Lezhnina & Kismihók, 2022). Taken together, these findings suggest that all facets of ICT engagement matter, with perceived autonomy often playing a particularly prominent role.

A growing body of work indicates that ICT engagement helps to explain how ICT use relates to student performance. Several studies explicitly identify engagement or ICT-related attitudes as mediating mechanisms. For instance, student engagement mediates the relationship between ICT resources and academic achievement (Y. Wang & Wang, 2023). Cognitive-motivational engagement in ICT has been shown to mediate positively the effect of ICT use on academic outcomes (Li & Zhu, 2023), while students' autonomy and perceived competence in ICT are key factors influencing their use of ICT for educational purposes (Silva et al., 2024). Related evidence points to the role of attitudes toward ICT, especially autonomy, confidence and interest, which display strong positive associations with achievement (Courtney et al., 2022; Lim & Jung, 2019). In addition,

students' interest in ICT appears to foster ICT self-efficacy (Chen & Hu, 2020), which is itself positively related to performance. Overall, this line of research supports the view that ICT engagement acts as an intermediary channel through which ICT use, whose direct effects on achievement are often mixed, can generate more consistently positive outcomes for students.

Although the predominant pattern is positive, there are some studies reporting null or even negative associations. For example, positive attitudes and experiences with ICT, including enjoyment, self-efficacy, autonomy and learning, do not significantly influence reading and information literacy in the Slovenian context (Lang et al., 2024), and in some European countries attitudes toward ICT do not explain variation in performance (Arpacı et al., 2021). In other cases, higher ICT interest is negatively associated with achievement (Gubbels et al., 2020). These contributions provide a useful reminder that ICT engagement does not automatically translate into better outcomes, and that its effects may depend on contextual factors and on the specific ways in which engagement is expressed.

The evidence in this section suggests that ICT engagement constitutes a crucial dimension for understanding the link between ICT use and student performance. Most studies find positive relationships between ICT engagement and academic outcomes, and several contributions indicate that this dimension plays a mediating role in the ICT achievement nexus. Within this construct, perceived autonomy in ICT emerges as particularly influential component, even though all spheres of ICT engagement contribute to shaping students' learning trajectories.

3.4 Inequalities across gender, socioeconomic status and performance levels

One of the main findings of this review concerns the role of technology in either increasing or reducing educational inequalities. This dimension is difficult to capture, especially because most of the available evidence relies on cross sectional data, and more specific experimental studies would be needed for stronger causal interpretations. Nonetheless, our analysis highlights two main inequality issues.

First, the role of the gender gap clearly emerges. Several studies focus on this dimension as a primary topic (Alagumalai & Buchdahl, 2021; Drabowicz, 2014; Erdogdu & Erdogdu, 2023; Meggiolaro, 2018; Tømte & Hatlevik, 2011; Xu, 2016), while others address it as a secondary issue (M. Kim & Kim, 2023; Kong et al., 2022; Lim & Jung, 2019; Navarro-Martinez & Peña-Acuña, 2022; Rico-Juan et al., 2024; Zhong, 2011). Overall, this literature shows that male students tend to have greater access to ICT resources, and Xu (2016) report that sons have more access to technological resources. However, access alone is not sufficient to describe the digital divide. Tømte and Hatlevik (2011) show that the digital divide is no longer about access, since virtually all students have ICT,

but rather about differences in use and self efficacy, which underlines the important role of schools in monitoring students' ICT practices and reducing these inequalities. Male students make more intensive use of ICT for almost all activities, except communication (Drabowicz, 2014), and Meggiolaro (2018) find that ICT is used more by boys and tends to strengthen their performance, with stronger positive effects of gaming and information management for males. In the same line, Alagumalai and Buchdahl (2021) show that boys outperform girls in all three literacy processes interpret, employ and formulate. Consistently, M. Kim and Kim (2023) and Zhong (2011) report that boys are more often placed in high ICT familiarity profiles. Kong et al. (2022) show that student attitudes toward the use of digital devices are positively associated with digital reading achievement, with a stronger association for boys. Navarro-Martinez and Peña-Acuña (2022) find that excessive use of technology and social networks impairs performance, especially for male students, who start at an earlier age and are more likely to use social media for online gaming. Conversely, Erdogdu and Erdogdu (2023) report a reversed gender gap, showing that girls have better attitudes towards ICT than boys and Karlsson (2022) that girls benefit slightly more than boys from home computer use.

Second, the literature documents inequalities among students, with specific attention to low performing students and those with low socioeconomic status (SES) (Falck et al., 2018; Giambona & Porcu, 2015; Hahnel et al., 2023; H. Kim et al., 2021; M. Kim & Kim, 2023; Loh et al., 2023; Ma et al., 2019; Park & Weng, 2020; Tan & Hew, 2017; Vargas-Montoya et al., 2023, 2024; Veselkova, 2024). The extant research indicates that ICT is linked to an increase in educational inequality, with a strong connection to the socio-economic context. (Alvarez-Garcia, Ibar-Alonso, & Arenas-Parra, 2024; Bonacini & Murat, 2023). Vargas-Montoya et al. (2024) find that ICT use at school positively affects gifted students' mathematics performance, while it negatively affects lower achieving students, particularly in mathematics, suggesting a differentiated approach to ICT based education. Loh et al. (2023) show that high SES students tend to have more beneficial ICT resources, which contributes to the social reproduction of educational inequality. Jeong et al. (2024) noted that a student's ICT use and competence were significantly associated with their SES. Conversely, other studies show a positive role of ICT in inequality situations, highlighting a significant positive impact of ICT investment on students from economically disadvantaged backgrounds and its potential as a tool for social equity in education (Cabras & Tena Horrillo, 2016; Giambona & Porcu, 2015; Gómez-Fernández & Mediavilla, 2021; Tan & Hew, 2017; Veselkova, 2024). In addition, the integration of ICT at school plays a compensatory role for digital inequalities at home, since school ICT integration significantly influences the frequency and quality of ICT use at home, whereas SES mainly affects ICT access (González-Betancor et al., 2021). At the same time, low performing students appear particularly vulnerable, as they are often characterised by a lack of interest in ICT use and by patterns of ICT abuse (J. Hu et al., 2023). Overall, this body of evidence suggests that access to ICT can improve the performance of low

performing and disadvantaged students, while in terms of actual use high SES and high performing students tend to benefit more (Jeong et al., 2024). In this context, school policies and teachers are crucial in strengthening ICT skills and engagement among low performing students.

3.5 Teachers and school role

A key topic concerns the role of teachers and the school context in the association between ICT and student performance. The teacher is considered an important factor in reforms at the level of the school that aim to integrate technology into the classroom (Scherer et al., 2019). Teachers are encouraged to bring technology into their instruction, using it to support learning processes or to conduct formative assessment (Shute & Rahimi, 2017). This shift calls for a purposeful and consistent use of technology within teaching and learning environments (C. Hu, 2017; Siddiq et al., 2016). As Jeong et al. (2024) demonstrate, teachers' ICT use has been shown to be positively linked to student achievement, with a stronger effect observed when students feel confident in using digital tools. Furthermore, it has been determined that national ICT development does not invariably result in increased classroom integration. Teachers in highly advanced countries may, for instance, utilise ICT less frequently than their counterparts in less developed contexts. Silva et al. (2024) underline that teacher satisfaction and the need for ICT training also play an important role. Hew and Tan (2016) show that schools with stronger IT resources, clearer ICT expectations and policies, and teachers who hold student centred and problem solving oriented beliefs display higher levels of ICT integration. According to Borgonovi et al. (2023), teacher enthusiasm moderates the relationship between ICT use and boredom, reducing the likelihood that students experience boredom. Gómez-García et al. (2021) find that teachers who use ICT related social networks in class form a small and distinct group, being generally younger, less experienced, and more often male than their colleagues. Xiao and Hew (2022) show that support at the level of the school, in terms of devices and teachers' technological capacity, strengthens the positive effects of ICT related psychological factors and reduces the negative impact of social interaction. Eickelmann et al. (2017) report that school leadership and strategies for ICT use significantly influence the integration of ICT in mathematics lessons, although the effects on achievement vary across countries. In other words, low performing students benefit more from the complementarity between students' digital competence and teachers' ICT integration than high performing students (Jeong et al., 2024). This body of evidence suggests that teachers and the school environment play a pivotal role in understanding the relationship between ICT and student achievement. The role of teachers in shaping how ICT relates to students is substantial and remains central to policies aimed at expanding the use of digital technologies in schools. Supporting teachers in learning how to use technology effectively in their instruction is a key challenge that policymakers need

to address.

4 Conclusion

Our systematic review of ILSA-based studies on the role of ICT in students' performance in the European context confirms that this is a highly heterogeneous field, both in terms of methods and how ICT is conceptualised. A key source of this heterogeneity is time. Between the early 2000s and 2025, the technologies used in schools have changed substantially. As a result, both policy and research have moved from focusing mainly on access and availability to focusing on how ICT is used in teaching and learning, how much use is appropriate for students, and which digital skills are needed for ICT to support learning. Over the same period, policies have shifted from expanding access across more schools to placing greater emphasis on the quality of devices, platforms, and digital infrastructure, and on the conditions that allow ICT to be used effectively in the classroom.

The primary research question guiding this study is: What research methods have been employed to study the relationship between ICT and student performance? We classified the literature by methodological approach. Although association analyses remain dominant, the review shows that causal identification is feasible within ILSA frameworks. Recent work also uses machine learning to model complex and non-linear patterns. Within associative studies, hierarchical linear models remain the standard tool. Structural equation models are used more often and provide a complementary view, where ICT is treated as a mediating component of the education production function. By contrast, efficiency analysis plays a comparatively minor role. Only a handful of contributions include ICT as an input in school-level efficiency assessments. This is clearly an area of importance for the next generation of studies in this field. Our second research question concerns the classification of ICT: Which aspects of ICT have the strongest association with student performance? We addressed this by distinguishing three broad dimensions: ICT availability, ICT use, and ICT engagement. Early contributions focused heavily on availability, but this dimension has gradually lost relevance in European contexts as access has become nearly universal. Contemporary research has shifted its focus towards ICT use, moving beyond simple frequency indicators towards specifications that explicitly capture non-linearities. A recurring finding in this strand of research is an inverted-U relationship between ICT use and achievement, where moderate levels of use are associated with the most favourable outcomes. ICT engagement has emerged as a pivotal and increasingly theorised dimension. The evidence points to a positive association between students' engagement with ICT and their academic performance, and suggests that engagement mediates the relationship between ICT use and achievement, particularly through constructs such as perceived autonomy. Together, these findings indicate that a comprehensive understanding of the academic effects of ICT requires joint consideration of both ICT use and ICT engagement. Future research and policy discussion

should recognise the centrality of students' behavioural and motivational engagement with digital technologies in shaping educational performance.

A cross-cutting theme emerging from the review concerns the role of ICT in educational inequalities. At first glance, the evidence appears mixed, with some studies suggesting that ICT can compress achievement gaps and others pointing to the risk of exacerbating them. However, a closer examination highlights the critical role of teachers and schools in shaping distributional effects. When ICT is integrated strategically to support low-achieving students and those from disadvantaged backgrounds, it can expand learning opportunities and narrow gaps. This body of work indicates that teachers and the broader school environment are crucial in shaping how ICT affects student achievement, especially for disadvantaged students. Teachers remain central to any policy aimed at expanding digital technologies in schools, and a key challenge for policymakers is to ensure that teachers receive adequate support, training and resources to integrate ICT effectively into their instructional practice.

From a policy point of view, ICT may bring especially large benefits in specific situations that current ILSA data do not capture well. One example concerns students with special educational needs, who may benefit from personalised and assistive uses of ICT. This potential is often mentioned in policy discussions, but existing ILSAs include only limited information to study these targeted uses in a rigorous way. This lack of suitable measures is an important limitation of the current evidence and points to a clear priority for future data collection.

Overall, the evidence indicates that the most relevant ICT dimensions are quality of use and student engagement, with attitudes acting as a key mediating mechanism. ICT integration may also reproduce or widen existing inequalities, suggesting that complementarities with teacher skills and pedagogical practices are central to its effectiveness. While questioning the presence of technology in schools is a useful dimension, it is essential to clarify the conditions under which ICT can be shown to improve academic performance.

The conclusions of this review suggest three clear priorities for future research. First, although ILSAs are cross-national studies, existing work shows that stronger causal evidence is possible when researchers use careful designs and appropriate quantitative methods. Building more of this evidence would improve what we know about the learning gains that can be attributed to ICT. Second, studies should link ICT use to educational equity more directly, by looking at whether the relationship between ICT and achievement differs across socio-economic groups and school settings, not only on average outcomes. Third, the relationship between ICT and efficiency requires much greater attention. A key argument for investing in digital technology is that it could enhance learning outcomes for each unit of input. However, the evidence base remains limited. Further work on efficiency would clarify whether investment in infrastructure, access and teacher training is associated with higher achievement for a given level of resources. This would show

whether ICT is linked to more efficient educational production. In conclusion, ICT is now part of everyday schooling in European systems. However, technology does not improve learning on its own. What matters is the quality of use in classrooms and the fit with the curriculum, teaching practices, teacher skills, and students' needs. Future work needs to move past access narratives and concentrate on the practical conditions that allow ICT to improve learning, support inclusion, and increase efficiency in a fast-changing digital environment.

References

- Acar, T. (2023). Breaking the cycle: The mediating effects of reading, mathematical and ICT literacy skills on financial success in youth. *Review of Education*, 11(3).
- Agasisti, T., Gil-Izquierdo, M., & Han, S. (2020). ICT use at home for school-related tasks: What is the effect on a student's achievement? Empirical evidence from OECD PISA data. *Education Economics*, 28(6), 601–620.
- Ahn, J. (2020). Unequal loneliness in the digitalized classroom: Two loneliness effects of school computers and lessons for sustainable education in the e-learning era. *Sustainability*, 12(19).
- Alagumalai, S., & Buchdahl, N. (2021). PISA 2012: Examining the influence of prior knowledge, time-on-task, school-level effects on achievements in mathematical literacy processes – interpret, employ and formulate. *Australian Journal of Education*, 65(2), 173–194.
- Alderete, M., Di Meglio, G., & Formichella, M. (2017). ICT access and educational performance: A relationship enhanced by ICT use? Analysis for Spain. *Revista de Educacion*, 2017(377), 54–79.
- Alvarez-Garcia, M., Arenas-Parra, M., & Ibar-Alonso, R. (2024). Uncovering student profiles. An explainable cluster analysis approach to PISA 2022. *Computers & Education*, 223, 105166.
- Alvarez-Garcia, M., Ibar-Alonso, R., & Arenas-Parra, M. (2024). A comprehensive framework for explainable cluster analysis. *Information Sciences*, 663, 120282.
- Angrist, J., & Lavy, V. (2002). New evidence on classroom computers and pupil learning. *The Economic Journal*, 112(482), 735–765.
- Areepattamannil, S., & Santos, I. (2019). Adolescent students' perceived information and communication technology (ICT) competence and autonomy: Examining links to dispositions toward science in 42 countries. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 98, 50–58.
- Arpacı, S., Mercan, F. Ç., & Arıkan, S. (2021). The differential relationships between pisa 2015 science performance and, ICT availability, ICT use and attitudes toward ICT across regions: Evidence from 35 countries. *Education and Information Technologies*, 26(5), 6299–6318.
- Athey, S., & Imbens, G. W. (2017). The state of applied econometrics: Causality and policy evaluation. *Journal of Economic Perspectives*, 31(2), 3–32.
- Athey, S., & Imbens, G. W. (2019). Machine learning methods that economists should know about. *Annual Review of Economics*, 11(1), 685–725.
- Aydin, M. (2022). A multilevel modeling approach to investigating factors impacting computer and information literacy: ICILS Korea and Finland sample. *Education and Information Technologies*, 27(2), 1675–1703.

- Barra, C., & Boccia, M. (2022). What matters in educational performance? Evidence from OECD and non-OECD countries. *Quality and Quantity*, *56*(6), 4335–4394.
- Barro, R. J., & Lee, J. W. (2013). A new data set of educational attainment in the world, 1950–2010. *Journal of Development Economics*, *104*, 184–198.
- Benítez Díaz, L., Sevillano García, M., & Vázquez Cano, E. (2019). Effects on academic performance in secondary students according to the use of ICT. *International Journal of Educational Research and Innovation*, *12*, 90–108.
- Bhutoria, A., & Aljabri, N. (2022). Patterns of cognitive returns to information and communication technology (ICT) use of 15-year-olds: Global evidence from a hierarchical linear modeling approach using PISA 2018. *Computers & Education*, *181*.
- Biagi, F., & Loi, M. (2013). Measuring ICT use and learning outcomes: Evidence from recent econometric studies. *European Journal of Education*, *48*(1), 28–42.
- Bingimlas, K. A. (2009). Barriers to the successful integration of ICT in teaching and learning environments: A review of the literature. *Eurasia Journal of Mathematics, Science and Technology Education*, *5*(3), 235–245.
- Blurton, C. (1999). New directions of ICT-use in education. In *World communication and information report 1999–2000*. UNESCO.
- Bollen, K. A. (1989). *Structural equations with latent variables* (1st). Wiley.
- Bonacini, L., & Murat, M. (2023). Beyond the covid-19 pandemic: Remote learning and education inequalities. *Empirica*, *50*(1), 207–236.
- Borgonovi, F., Pokropek, M., & Pokropek, A. (2023). Relations between academic boredom, academic achievement, ICT use, and teacher enthusiasm among adolescents. *Computers & Education*, *200*.
- Borgonovi, F., & Pokropek, M. (2021). The evolution of the association between ICT use and reading achievement in 28 countries. *Computers & Education Open*, *2*, 100047.
- Böttger, T., & Zierer, K. (2024). To ban or not to ban? A rapid review on the impact of smartphone bans in schools on social well-being and academic performance. *Education Sciences*, *14*(8), 906.
- Brand, J. E., Zhou, X., & Xie, Y. (2023). Recent developments in causal inference and machine learning. *Annual Review of Sociology*, *49*(1), 81–110.
- Briscoe, S., Bethel, A., & Rogers, M. (2020). Conduct and reporting of citation searching in cochrane systematic reviews: A cross-sectional study. *Research Synthesis Methods*, *11*(2), 169–180.
- Bulut, O., & Cutumisu, M. (2018). When technology does not add up: ICT use negatively predicts mathematics and science achievement for Finnish and Turkish students in PISA 2012. *Journal of Educational Multimedia and Hypermedia*, *27*(1), 25–42.

- Cabras, S., & Tena Horrillo, J. (2016). A bayesian non-parametric modeling to estimate student response to ICT investment. *Journal of Applied Statistics*, *43*(14), 2627–2642.
- Caena, F. (2019). Developing a european framework for the digital competence of educators: The role of policy coordination and mutual learning. *European Journal of Education*, *54*(4), 552–568.
- Campbell, M., Edwards, E. J., Pennell, D., Poed, S., Lister, V., Gillett-Swan, J., Kelly, A., Zec, D., & Nguyen, T.-A. (2024). Evidence for and against banning mobile phones in schools: A scoping review. *Journal of Psychologists and Counsellors in Schools*, *34*(3), 242–265.
- Casillas Martín, S., Cabezas González, M., & García Peñalvo, F. J. (2020). Digital competence of early childhood education teachers: Attitude, knowledge and use of ICT. *European Journal of Teacher Education*, *43*(2), 210–223.
- Chalmers, I., Hedges, L. V., & Cooper, H. (2002). A brief history of research synthesis. *Evaluation & the Health Professions*, *25*(1), 12–37.
- Chen, X., & Hu, J. (2020). ICT-related behavioral factors mediate the relationship between adolescents' ICT interest and their ICT self-efficacy: Evidence from 30 countries. *Computers & Education*, *159*, 104004.
- Chernozhukov, V., Hansen, C., Kallus, N., Spindler, M., & Syrgkanis, V. (2024). *Applied causal inference powered by ML and AI* [Version available on arXiv]. arXiv: 2403.02467. <https://www.causalmml-book.org>
- Comi, S. L., Argentin, G., Gui, M., Origo, F., & Pagani, L. (2017). Is it the way they use it? Teachers, ICT and student achievement. *Economics of Education Review*, *56*, 24–39.
- Cordero, J. M., Cristóbal, V., & Santín, D. (2018). Causal inference on education policies: A survey of empirical studies using PISA, TIMSS and PIRLS. *Journal of Economic Surveys*, *32*(3), 878–915.
- Costa, D., & Chen, C.-W. (2023). Exploring the relationship between process data and contextual variables among Scandinavian students on PISA 2012 mathematics tasks. *Large-Scale Assessments in Education*, *11*(1).
- Courtney, M., Karakus, M., Ersozlu, Z., & Nurumov, K. (2022). The influence of ICT use and related attitudes on students' math and science performance: Multilevel analyses of the last decade's PISA surveys. *Large-Scale Assessments in Education*, *10*(1).
- Cronin, B. (2002). The digital divide.(the dean's list). *Library Journal*, *127*(3), 48–49.
- De Witte, K., & Rogge, N. (2014). Does ICT matter for effectiveness and efficiency in mathematics education? *Computers & Education*, *75*, 173–184.
- Deci, E. L., & Ryan, R. M. (2000). The "What" and "Why" of goal pursuits: Human needs and the self-determination of behavior. *Psychological Inquiry*, *11*(4), 227–268.

- Dong, F., & Kula, M. (2023). Digital device use and scientific literacy: An examination using Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA) 2015 data. *Education Economics*, 31(3), 288–312.
- Drabowicz, T. (2014). Gender and digital usage inequality among adolescents: A comparative study of 39 countries. *Computers & Education*, 74, 98–111.
- DuGoff, E. H., Schuler, M., & Stuart, E. A. (2014). Generalizing observational study results: Applying propensity score methods to complex surveys. *Health Services Research*, 49(1), 284–303.
- Eickelmann, B., Gerick, J., & Koop, C. (2017). ICT use in mathematics lessons and the mathematics achievement of secondary school students by international comparison: Which role do school level factors play? *Education and Information Technologies*, 22(4), 1527–1551.
- Elsevier. (2025). Scopus database.
- Erdogdu, F. (2022a). ICT, learning environment and student characteristics as potential cross-country predictors of academic achievement. *Education and Information Technologies*, 27(5), 7135–7159.
- Erdogdu, F. (2022b). Potential predictors of student attainment: A longitudinal study at global level. *Education and Information Technologies*, 27(7), 9689–9711.
- Erdogdu, F., & Erdogdu, E. (2023). Understanding students’ attitudes towards ICT. *Interactive Learning Environments*, 31(10), 7467–7485.
- European Commission. (2013). *Survey of schools: ICT in education – benchmarking access, use and attitudes to technology in europe’s schools*.
- European Commission. (2020). Digital education action plan (2021–2027): Resetting education and training for the digital age.
- Eurostat. (2024). *Individuals who have never used the internet by educational attainment level, sex and age (% of individuals aged 16–74) [isoc_{ci}in_h]* [Eurostat database]. https://doi.org/10.2908/isoc_ci_in_h
- Falck, O., Mang, C., & Woessmann, L. (2018). Virtually no effect? Different uses of classroom computers and their effect on student achievement. *Oxford Bulletin of Economics and Statistics*, 80(1), 1–38.
- Färe, R., Grosskopf, S., & Pasurka Jr, C. A. (2007). Environmental production functions and environmental directional distance functions. *Energy*, 32(7), 1055–1066.
- Fariña, P., San Martín, E., Preiss, D., Claro, M., & Jara, I. (2015). Measuring the relation between computer use and reading literacy in the presence of endogeneity. *Computers & Education*, 80, 176–186.
- Fayda-Kinik, F. S., & Cetin, M. (2025). ICT and academic achievement in secondary education: A hierarchical linear modelling. *Journal of Computer Assisted Learning*, 41(1), e13070.
- Feenstra, R. C., Inklaar, R., & Timmer, M. P. (2015). The next generation of the penn world table. *American Economic Review*, 105(10), 3150–3182.

- Feliciano, D., López-Torres, L., & Santín, D. (2021). One laptop per child? Using production frontiers for evaluating the Escuela 2.0 program in Spain. *Mathematics*, *9*(20), 2600.
- Fernández-Gutiérrez, M., Gimenez, G., & Calero, J. (2020). Is the use of ICT in education leading to higher student outcomes? Analysis from the Spanish autonomous communities. *Computers & Education*, *157*.
- Ferraro, S. (2018). Is information and communication technology satisfying educational needs at school? *Computers & Education*, *122*, 194–204.
- Ghobadi, S., & Ghobadi, Z. (2013). Digital divide and interrelated access gaps: A cognitive investigation. *European Conference on Information Systems*, Utrecht, The Netherlands, June.
- Giambona, F., & Porcu, M. (2015). Student background determinants of reading achievement in Italy. A quantile regression analysis. *International Journal of Educational Development*, *44*, 95–107.
- Gil-Flores, J., & García-Gómez, S. (2017). The importance of teaching practices in relation to regional educational policies in explaining PISA achievement. *Revista de Educacion*, *2017*(378), 52–74.
- Gil-Flores, J., Torres-Gordillo, J.-J., & Perera-Rodríguez, V.-H. (2012). The role of online reader experience in explaining students' performance in digital reading. *Computers & Education*, *59*(2), 653–660.
- Gilleece, L., & Eivers, E. (2018). Characteristics associated with paper-based and online reading in Ireland: Findings from PIRLS and ePIRLS 2016. *International Journal of Educational Research*, *91*, 16–27.
- Gimenez, G., & Vargas-Montoya, L. (2021). ICT use and successful learning: The role of the stock of human capital. *Mathematics*, *9*(14).
- Goldhammer, F., Gniewosz, G., & Zylka, J. (2016). ICT engagement in learning environments. In *Assessing contexts of learning: An international perspective* (pp. 331–351).
- Gómez-Fernández, N., & Mediavilla, M. (2021). Exploring the relationship between information and communication technologies (ICT) and academic performance: A multilevel analysis for Spain. *Socio-Economic Planning Sciences*, *77*, 101009.
- Gómez-García, M., Boumadan, M., Soto-Varela, R., & Gutiérrez-García, Á. (2021). What are the factors that influence the use of social networks as a means to serve pedagogy? *Texto Livre*, *14*(1), e25420.
- González-Betancor, S. M., López-Puig, A. J., & Cardenal, M. E. (2021). Digital inequality at home. The school as compensatory agent. *Computers & Education*, *168*, 104195.
- Gorjón, L., & Osés, A. (2023). The negative impact of information and communication technologies overuse on student performance: Evidence from OECD countries. *Journal of Educational Computing Research*, *61*(4), 723–765.
- Gough, D., Thomas, J., & Oliver, S. (2017). *An introduction to systematic reviews*. SAGE.

- Gubbels, J., Swart, N., & Groen, M. (2020). Everything in moderation: ICT and reading performance of dutch 15-year-olds. *Large-Scale Assessments in Education*, 8(1).
- Güzeller, C., & Akin, A. (2014). Relationship between ICT variables and mathematics achievement based on PISA 2006 database: International evidence. *Turkish Online Journal of Educational Technology*, 13(1), 184–192.
- Hahnel, C., Ramalingam, D., Kroehne, U., & Goldhammer, F. (2023). Patterns of reading behaviour in digital hypertext environments. *Journal of Computer Assisted Learning*, 39(3), 737–750.
- Hew, K. F., & Tan, C. Y. (2016). Predictors of information technology integration in secondary schools: Evidence from a large scale study of more than 30,000 students. *PLoS One*, 11(12), e0168547.
- Hopfenbeck, T. N., Lenkeit, J., El Masri, Y., Cantrell, K., Ryan, J., & Baird, J.-A. (2018). Lessons learned from PISA: A systematic review of peer-reviewed articles on the programme for international student assessment. *Scandinavian Journal of Educational Research*, 62(3), 333–353.
- Hori, R., & Fujii, M. (2021). Impact of using ICT for learning purposes on self-efficacy and persistence: Evidence from PISA 2018. *Sustainability*, 13(11).
- Hu, C. (2017). Students, computers and learning: Where is the connection? *Education and Information Technologies*, 22(6), 2665–2670.
- Hu, J., Peng, Y., & Chen, X. (2023). Decoding contextual factors differentiating adolescents' high, average, and low digital reading performance through machine-learning methods. *IEEE Transactions on Learning Technologies*, 16(4), 516–527.
- Hu, J., & Wang, Y. (2022). Influence of students' perceptions of instruction quality on their digital reading performance in 29 OECD countries: A multilevel analysis. *Computers & Education*, 189.
- Hu, J., & Yu, R. (2021). The effects of ICT-based social media on adolescents' digital reading performance: A longitudinal study of PISA 2009, PISA 2012, PISA 2015 and PISA 2018. *Computers & Education*, 175.
- Hu, J., & Hu, J. (2024). The influence of age at first regular digital device access on digital reading performance: The mediating effect of cognitive flexibility. *Humanities and Social Sciences Communications*, 11(1), 1–18.
- Hu, X., Gong, Y., Lai, C., & Leung, F. (2018). The relationship between ICT and student literacy in mathematics, reading, and science across 44 countries: A multilevel analysis. *Computers & Education*, 125, 1–13.
- Huber, M. (2023). *Causal analysis: Impact evaluation and causal machine learning with applications in R*.
- International Telecommunication Union. (2015). *Measuring the information society report 2015*. International Telecommunication Union. <https://www.itu.int/en/ITU-D/Statistics/Pages/publications/mis2015.aspx>

- Jeong, D., Moon, H., Jeong, S., & Moon, C. (2024). Digital capital accumulation in schools, teachers, and students and academic achievement: Cross-country evidence from the PISA 2018. *International Journal of Educational Development*, 107.
- Joshi, D. R., Sharma Chapai, K. P., Upadhayaya, P. R., Adhikari, K. P., & Belbase, S. (2025). Effect of using digital resources on mathematics achievement: Results from PISA 2022. *Cogent Education*, 12(1), 2488161.
- Juhaňák, L., Zounek, J., Záleská, K., Bárta, O., & Vlčková, K. (2018). The relationship between students' ICT use and their school performance: Evidence from PISA 2015 in the Czech Republic. *Orbis Scholae*, 12(2), 37–64.
- Juhaňák, L., Zounek, J., Záleská, K., Bárta, O., & Vlčková, K. (2019). The relationship between the age at first computer use and students' perceived competence and autonomy in ICT usage: A mediation analysis. *Computers & Education*, 141, 103614.
- Kadijevich, D. (2015). A dataset from TIMSS to examine the relationship between computer use and mathematics achievement. *British Journal of Educational Technology*, 46(5), 984–987.
- Karakolidis, A., Pitsia, V., & Cosgrove, J. (2022). Multilevel modelling of international large-scale assessment data. In *Methodology for multilevel modeling in educational research: Concepts and applications* (pp. 141–159).
- Karlsson, L. (2022). Computers in education: The association between computer use and test scores in primary school. *Education Inquiry*, 13(1), 56–85.
- Kessel, D., Hardardottir, H. L., & Tyrefors, B. (2020). The impact of banning mobile phones in Swedish secondary schools. *Economics of Education Review*, 77, 102009.
- Kim, H., Yi, P., & Hong, J. (2021). Are schools digitally inclusive for all? Profiles of school digital inclusion using PISA 2018. *Computers & Education*, 170.
- Kim, M., & Kim, H. (2023). Profiles of students' ICT use in high-performing countries in PISA 2018. *Computers in the Schools*, 40(3), 262–281.
- Kitchenham, B., Pretorius, R., Budgen, D., Brereton, O. P., Turner, M., Niazi, M., & Linkman, S. (2010). Systematic literature reviews in software engineering—a tertiary study. *Information and Software Technology*, 52(8), 792–805.
- Kong, Y., Seo, Y. S., & Zhai, L. (2022). ICT and digital reading achievement: A cross-national comparison using PISA 2018 data. *International Journal of Educational Research*, 111, 101912.
- Kubiatko, M., & Vlckova, K. (2010). The relationship between ICT use and science knowledge for Czech students: A secondary analysis of PISA 2006. *International Journal of Science and Mathematics Education*, 8(3), 523–543.
- Kunina-Habenicht, O., & Goldhammer, F. (2020). ICT engagement: A new construct and its assessment in PISA 2015. *Large-Scale Assessments in Education*, 8(1), 6.
- Lai, J. W., & Bower, M. (2019). How is the use of technology in education evaluated? A systematic review. *Computers & Education*, 133, 27–42.

- Lang, V., Špernjak, A., & Šorgo, A. (2024). The relationship between the daily use of digital technologies and the reading and information literacy skills of 15-year-old students. *European Journal of Educational Research*, *13*(1).
- Lee, Y.-H., & Wu, J.-Y. (2012). The effect of individual differences in the inner and outer states of ICT on engagement in online reading activities and PISA 2009 reading literacy: Exploring the relationship between the old and new reading literacy. *Learning and Individual Differences*, *22*(3), 336–342.
- Lee, Y.-H., & Wu, J.-Y. (2013). The indirect effects of online social entertainment and information seeking activities on reading literacy. *Computers & Education*, *67*, 168–177.
- Lezhnina, O., & Kismihók, G. (2022). Combining statistical and machine learning methods to explore German students' attitudes towards ICT in PISA. *International Journal of Research & Method in Education*, *45*(2), 180–199.
- Li, S., & Petersen, K. (2022). Does ICT matter? Unfolding the complex multilevel structural relationship between technology use and academic achievements in PISA 2015. *Educational Technology and Society*, *25*(4), 43–55.
- Li, S., & Zhu, J. (2023). Cognitive-motivational engagement in ICT mediates the effect of ICT use on academic achievements: Evidence from 52 countries. *Computers & Education*, *204*.
- Liem, G., Martin, A., Anderson, M., Gibson, R., & Sudmalis, D. (2014). The role of arts-related information and communication technology use in problem solving and achievement: Findings from the programme for international student assessment. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, *106*(2), 348–363.
- Lim, H., & Jung, H. (2019). Factors related to digital reading achievement: A multi-level analysis using international large scale data. *Computers & Education*, *133*, 82–93.
- Lin, L., King, R., Fu, L., & Leung, S. (2024). Information and communication technology engagement and digital reading: How meta-cognitive strategies impact their relationship. *British Journal of Educational Technology*, *55*(1), 277–296.
- Liu, J., Aziku, M., Qiang, F., & Zhang, B. (2024). Leveraging professional learning communities in linking digital professional development and instructional integration: Evidence from 16,072 STEM teachers. *International Journal of STEM Education*, *11*(1), 56.
- Livingstone, S. (2012). Critical reflections on the benefits of ICT in education. *Oxford Review of Education*, *38*(1), 9–24.
- Loh, R., Kraaykamp, G., & Van Hek, M. (2023). Student ICT resources and intergenerational transmission of educational inequality: Testing implications of a reproduction and mobility perspective. *European Sociological Review*, *39*(5), 804–819.
- Luu, K., & Freeman, J. G. (2011). An analysis of the relationship between information and communication technology (ICT) and scientific literacy in Canada and Australia. *Computers & Education*, *56*(4), 1072–1082.

- Ma, J.-H., Vachon, T., & Cheng, S. (2019). National income, political freedom, and investments in R&D and education: A comparative analysis of the second digital divide among 15-year-old students. *Social Indicators Research, 144*(1), 133–166.
- Martínez-Gautier, D., Garrido-Yserte, R., & Gallo-Rivera, M.-T. (2021). Educational performance and ICTs: Availability, use, misuse and context. *Journal of Business Research, 135*, 173–182.
- Marzano, R. J., & Kendall, J. S. (2006). *The new taxonomy of educational objectives*.
- Meggiolaro, S. (2018). Information and communication technologies use, gender and mathematics achievement: Evidence from Italy. *Social Psychology of Education, 21*(2), 497–516.
- Mergoni, A., Soncin, M., & Agasisti, T. (2023). The effect of ICT on schools' efficiency: Empirical evidence on 23 european countries. *Omega, 119*.
- Moher, D., Liberati, A., Tetzlaff, J., & Altman, D. G. (2009). Preferred reporting items for systematic reviews and meta-analyses: The PRISMA statement. *PLoS medicine, 6*(7), e1000097.
- Mullainathan, S., & Spiess, J. (2017). Machine learning: An applied econometric approach. *Journal of Economic Perspectives, 31*(2), 87–106.
- Navarro-Martinez, O., & Peña-Acuña, B. (2022). Technology usage and academic performance in the PISA 2018 report. *Journal of New Approaches in Educational Research, 11*(1), 130–145.
- Netten, A., Voeten, M., Droop, M., & Verhoeven, L. (2014). Sociocultural and educational factors for reading literacy decline in the Netherlands in the past decade. *Learning and Individual Differences, 32*, 9–18.
- Notten, N., & Kraaykamp, G. (2009). Home media and science performance: A cross-national study. *Educational Research and Evaluation, 15*(4), 367–384.
- Odell, B., Galovan, A., & Cutumisu, M. (2020). The relation between ICT and science in PISA 2015 for Bulgarian and Finnish students. *Eurasia Journal of Mathematics, Science and Technology Education, 16*(6), 1–15.
- OECD. (2003). *Are students ready for a technology-rich world? What PISA says*. OECD Publishing. Paris.
- OECD. (2023). *Shaping digital education: Enabling factors for quality, equity and efficiency*. OECD Publishing. Paris.
- OECD. (2025). *Policies for the digital transformation of school education: Evidence from the policy survey on school education in the digital age*. OECD Education Working Papers. Paris.
- Page, M. J., McKenzie, J. E., Bossuyt, P. M., Boutron, I., Hoffmann, T. C., Mulrow, C. D., Shamseer, L., Tetzlaff, J. M., Akl, E. A., Brennan, S. E., et al. (2021). The PRISMA 2020 statement: An updated guideline for reporting systematic reviews. *BMJ, 372*.

- Park, S., & Weng, W. (2020). The relationship between ICT-related factors and student academic achievement and the moderating effect of country economic indexes across 39 countries: Using multilevel structural equation modelling. *Educational Technology and Society*, *23*(3), 1–15.
- Peng, Y., Wang, Y., & Hu, J. (2023). Examining ICT attitudes, use and support in blended learning settings for students' reading performance: Approaches of artificial intelligence and multilevel model. *Computers & Education*, *203*.
- Petko, D., Cantieni, A., & Prasse, D. (2017). Perceived quality of educational technology matters: A secondary analysis of students ICT use, ICT-related attitudes, and PISA 2012 test scores. *Journal of Educational Computing Research*, *54*(8), 1070–1091.
- Pitzalis, M., & Porcu, M. (2024). Digital capital and cultural capital in education: Unravelling intersections and distinctions that shape social differentiation. *British Educational Research Journal*, *50*(6), 2753–2776.
- Pongsophon, P. (2024). Deciphering the layers of reading achievement: A multi-level analysis of student and school-level predictors in top-performing PIRLS 2021 countries. *British Educational Research Journal*, *50*(6), 2777–2798.
- Redecker, C., & Punie, Y. (2017). *European framework for the digital competence of educators: Digcompedu*.
- Rico-Juan, J. R., Pena-Acuna, B., & Navarro-Martinez, O. (2024). Holistic exploration of reading comprehension skills, technology and socioeconomic factors in Spanish teenagers. *Heliyon*, *10*(12).
- Rodrigues, M., & Biagi, F. (2017). *Digital technologies and learning outcomes of students from low socio-economic background: An analysis of PISA 2015*.
- Rosén, M., & Gustafsson, J.-E. (2016). Is computer availability at home causally related to reading achievement in grade 4? A longitudinal difference in differences approach to IEA data from 1991 to 2006. *Large-Scale Assessments in Education*, *4*(1).
- Rozgonjuk, D., Täht, K., & Vassil, K. (2021). Internet use at and outside of school in relation to low- and high-stakes mathematics test scores across 3 years. *International Journal of STEM Education*, *8*(1).
- Rutkowski, L., & Zhou, Y. (2014). Using structural equation models to analyze ILSA data. *Handbook of international large-scale assessment: Background, technical issues, and methods of data analysis*, 425–450.
- Ryan, R. M., & Deci, E. L. (2000). Self-determination theory and the facilitation of intrinsic motivation, social development, and well-being. *American Psychologist*, *55*(1), 68.
- Saal, P., Graham, M., & van Ryneveld, L. (2020). The relationship between integrating educational technology in mathematics education and the mathematics achievement of German students. *Eurasia Journal of Mathematics, Science and Technology Education*, *16*(12), 1–13.

- Saarinen, A., Lipsanen, J., Hintsanen, M., Huotilainen, M., & Keltikangas-Järvinen, L. (2021). The use of digital technologies at school and cognitive learning outcomes: A population-based study in Finland. *International Journal of Educational Psychology, 10*(1), 1–26.
- Scherer, R., Siddiq, F., & Tondeur, J. (2019). The technology acceptance model (TAM): A meta-analytic structural equation modeling approach to explaining teachers' adoption of digital technology in education. *Computers & education, 128*, 13–35.
- Schleicher, A. (2019). *PISA 2018: Insights and interpretations*. OECD Publishing.
- Selwyn, N., & Aagaard, J. (2021). Banning mobile phones from classrooms—an opportunity to advance understandings of technology addiction, distraction and cyberbullying. *British Journal of Educational Technology, 52*(1), 8–19.
- Shute, V. J., & Rahimi, S. (2017). Review of computer-based assessment for learning in elementary and secondary education. *Journal of Computer Assisted Learning, 33*(1), 1–19.
- Siddiq, F., Scherer, R., & Tondeur, J. (2016). Teachers' emphasis on developing students' digital information and communication skills (TEDDICS): A new construct in 21st century education. *Computers & Education, 92*, 1–14.
- Siebecke, D., & Jarl, M. (2022). Does the material well-being at schools successfully compensate for socioeconomic disadvantages? Analysis of resilient schools in Sweden. *Large-Scale Assessments in Education, 10*(1).
- Silva, J. C., Coelho Rodrigues, J., & Miguéis, V. L. (2024). Factors influencing the use of information and communication technologies by students for educational purposes. *Education and Information Technologies, 29*(8), 9313–9353.
- Skryabin, M., Zhang, J., Liu, L., & Zhang, D. (2015). How the ICT development level and usage influence student achievement in reading, mathematics, and science. *Computers & Education, 85*, 49–58.
- Spiezia, V. (2010). Does computer use increase educational achievements? Student-level evidence from PISA. *OECD Journal: Economic Studies, 127–148*.
- Steffens, K. (2014). ICT use and achievement in three european countries: What does PISA tell us? *European Educational Research Journal, 13*(5), 553–562.
- Sun, H., Xie, Y., & Lavonen, J. (2024). Effects of the use of ICT in schools on students' science higher-order thinking skills: Comparative study of China and Finland. *Research in Science & Technological Education, 42*(2), 276–293.
- Tan, C., & Hew, K. (2017). Information technology, mathematics achievement and educational equity in developed economies. *Educational Studies, 43*(4), 371–390.
- Tømte, C., & Hatlevik, O. E. (2011). Gender-differences in self-efficacy ICT related to various ICT-user profiles in Finland and Norway. How do self-efficacy, gender and ICT-user profiles relate to findings from pisa 2006. *Computers & Education, 57*(1), 1416–1424.

- Vargas-Montoya, L., Gimenez, G., & Fernández-Gutiérrez, M. (2023). ICT use for learning and students' outcomes: Does the country's development level matter? *Socio-Economic Planning Sciences*, *87*, 101550.
- Vargas-Montoya, L., Gimenez, G., & Tkacheva, L. (2024). Only gifted students benefit from ICT use at school in mathematics learning. *Education and Information Technologies*, *29*(7), 8301–8326.
- Varian, H. R. (2014). Big data: New tricks for econometrics. *Journal of Economic Perspectives*, *28*(2), 3–28.
- Vázquez-Cano, E., Gómez-Galán, J., Infante-Moro, A., & López-Meneses, E. (2020). Incidence of a non-sustainability use of technology on students' reading performance in PISA. *Sustainability*, *12*(2).
- Veselkova, M. (2024). The effect of computer availability on student achievement in Slovakia: Evidence from TIMSS and PIRLS. *European Education*, *56*(2), 155–178.
- Wager, S., & Athey, S. (2018). Estimation and inference of heterogeneous treatment effects using random forests. *Journal of the American Statistical Association*, *113*(523), 1228–1242.
- Wang, M., Yu, R., & Hu, J. (2023). The relationship between social media-related factors and student collaborative problem-solving achievement: An HLM analysis of 37 countries. *Education and Information Technologies*, *28*(11), 14071–14089.
- Wang, Y., & Wang, Y. (2023). Exploring the relationship between educational ICT resources, student engagement, and academic performance: A multilevel structural equation analysis based on PISA 2018 data. *Studies in Educational Evaluation*, *79*, 101308.
- Webbink, D. (2005). Causal effects in education. *Journal of Economic Surveys*, *19*(4), 535–560.
- Wittwer, J., & Senkbeil, M. (2008). Is students' computer use at home related to their mathematical performance at school? *Computers & Education*, *50*(4), 1558–1571.
- Xiao, Y., & Hew, K. (2022). The relationships among ICT-related psychological factors, school contextual factors and secondary students' reading performance: A multi-level analysis across 47 economies. *Journal of Educational Computing Research*, *60*(5), 1166–1196.
- Xu, J. (2016). Patriarchy, gendered spheres, or evolutionary adaptation? A cross-national examination of adolescent boys and girls access to home resources. *Chinese Sociological Review*, *48*(3), 209–247.
- Zhang, D., & Liu, L. (2016). How does ICT use influence students' achievements in math and science over time? Evidence from PISA 2000 to 2012. *Eurasia Journal of Mathematics, Science and Technology Education*, *12*(9), 2431–2449.
- Zhang, H., Tang, H., Zhou, Q., & Wang, F. (2025). Predictors of students' global competence in China, Germany, Turkey, and Mexico: A cross-cultural comparative study. *International Journal of Educational Development*, *113*, 103203.

- Zhong, Z.-J. (2011). From access to usage: The divide of self-reported digital skills among adolescents. *Computers & Education*, *56*(3), 736–746.
- Zylka, J., Christoph, G., Kroehne, U., Hartig, J., & Goldhammer, F. (2015). Moving beyond cognitive elements of ICT literacy: First evidence on the structure of ICT engagement. *Computers in Human Behavior*, *53*, 149–160.